

On the Number of Queries Required to Determine an Optimal Alternative (*Longer Version*)

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Abstract. Given the assumption that a user’s preference relation, on a finite set of alternatives, is in a particular family of preference relations, we consider the problem of how many queries are required to determine sufficient information about the preference relation that an alternative can be returned that is optimal for the user. We focus especially on queries based on comparisons between two alternatives and related forms of query. We consider both a fixed version of this problem, where the user is given a questionnaire (or batch of queries), and is asked to answer them all; and a dynamic, i.e., interactive, version, where the choice of query can depend on previous answers. We derive upper and lower bounds for the numbers of queries required, and give preference families that achieve these bounds; and we determine the solution of the batch problem for linear preference families.

This is a longer version of the ECAI 2025 paper [37]. As well as the proofs and auxiliary lemmas, this document includes two additional subsections: Section 2.7 discussing briefly the very large sizes of the search spaces, and Section 3.3 describing a more complex query language that achieves the logarithmic lower bound for both Depth and MQS. In addition, in Section 5.3, we state explicitly where the justifications of the bounds in Table 5.2 can be found.

1 Introduction

For finding an alternative that is optimal for a decision maker in an (e.g., multi-objective) optimisation problem, particular challenges are that (a) very often the decision support system will initially only have partial knowledge about the user’s preference relation over the alternatives; and (b) the user will often not be happy to answer a large number of elicitation queries. In recent years there has been substantial work on methods for incremental preference elicitation. If an informative sequence of queries can be found, then they can quickly cut down the space of potentially optimal alternatives, until one can be found that is necessarily optimal, given the user answers. This can require very many less queries than eliciting the full user preference relation. Often a linear model of some form is assumed, including MAUT (multi-attribute utility theory) models, or Generalised Additive or Choquet models. Since the potential search space is of astronomical size even for as little as ten alternatives, heuristic methods have been employed, especially based on the use of max regret, as a measure of how close an alternative is from being necessarily optimal.

In this paper we step back and take a more general formal view of the underlying problem of finding the best possible solutions (i.e., minimising the number of queries). It turns out that in fact there are some general results of a remarkably simple form. Given the assumption that a user’s preference relation, on a finite set A of alternatives, is in a particular family \mathcal{P} of preference relations, we consider the problem of how many queries are required to determine sufficient information about the preference relation that an optimal alternative can be returned. We only consider Boolean queries in this paper, i.e., where there are only two possible answers. For instance, we might consider a comparison query, such as whether or not one alternative β is preferred to another alternative γ . We assume that the user answers all queries correctly.

We focus on two kinds of task. The first is a non-dynamic version, seeking to find what we call a *questionnaire* (or a batch of queries); this is a set of queries, such that whichever set S of answers we receive, we can return an alternative $\beta(S)$ that will be optimal for the user. The *minimum questionnaire size* $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ is defined to be the cardinality of a smallest set of queries in query language \mathcal{Q} that is a questionnaire for preference family \mathcal{P} .

The second, more complicated task, corresponding to interactive elicitation, allows queries to be dependent on previous answers. For query language \mathcal{Q} , this can be represented as a \mathcal{Q} -query tree, which is a rooted binary tree (like in Figure 1 below), with a query in \mathcal{Q} associated with each body node, and the two child edges from the node corresponding to the two possible answers of the query; each leaf node is then associated with an alternative that is bound to be optimal given the answers on the edges from the root node to that leaf. Thus, for any possible sequence of user answers to queries, an optimal alternative can be returned. The depth of such a tree is defined to be the length of the longest directed path (from a root node to a leaf node).

The value $Depth(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ of the preference family \mathcal{P} with respect to the query language is defined to be smallest depth of any \mathcal{Q} -query tree for preference family \mathcal{P} . Since any questionnaire can be turned into a query tree, we always have $Depth(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$.

The important parameter $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ is defined to be the cardinality of a smallest set that includes at least one optimal alternative for every user model (i.e., preference relation) in \mathcal{P} . Basic analysis of binary trees leads to a lower bound of $\lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$ for $Depth(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$. We first consider query languages based on whether one, or a set of alternatives, is optimal, including a somewhat complex query language

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that always achieves the logarithmic lower bound.

A much more natural language $CompEx_A$ consists of comparison queries of the form *Is β better than γ ?*, for alternatives $\beta, \gamma \in A$. A very simple kind of query tree leads to a general upper bound of $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$ for $Depth(\mathcal{P}; CompEx_A)$, which we show is achieved for any family of approval preferences (where all non-optimal alternatives are equivalent). The logarithmic lower bound can be achieved for special \mathcal{P} , for instance, involving lexicographic orders.

Much of the previous work on incremental approaches (interleaving elicitation and optimisation) has focused on linear preference families. With a linear preference family \mathcal{P} , alternatives are associated with vectors in \mathbb{R}^p (each dimension corresponding to an objective), and there is an associated convex subset W of \mathbb{R}^p ; each preference relation in \mathcal{P} is of the form \succ_w for some $w \in W$, and $\alpha \succ_w \beta \iff w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \beta$. We prove a simple characterisation of $MQS(\mathcal{P}; CompEx_A)$ for linear \mathcal{P} ; we only need comparison queries between alternatives α and β that are adjacent in a certain sense.

Related Work

The theoretical work in this paper complements work on interactive optimisation techniques, when it is assumed (as we do in the formalism here) that the user's answers are consistent with their preferences; see e.g., [36, 14, 15, 27, 3, 8, 9, 26]. Such methods often use max regret [31] as a measure of closeness to being necessarily optimal, which is used for generating queries heuristically.

Our formal results relate to optimal policies for interactive optimisation, i.e., with optimal choices of query at each stage, in particular giving bounds on the smallest number of queries that can be guaranteed (depending on the assumptions made about the user preference model). As far as we are aware there has not been any previous study of optimal policies for this problem.

Many papers have made use of a linear user model based on a simple form of Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) [25, 21] for multi-objective reasoning, such as [35, 20], or other preference models that also lead to linear preferences families (i.e., linear in the weights vector, see e.g., the end of Section 3.1 of [33]), such as Choquet [5, 7, 30] or GAI user models [16].

In addition, there are methods that can deal with noisy user models, such as Bayesian methods [34, 11, 10, 35, 12] or other methods [32, 1, 23, 20].

We focus here on optimising for a single decision maker. Interactive optimisation techniques have also been developed for multi-agent optimisation, see for instance, [28, 4, 6, 29], with some theoretical analysis for voting rules, in terms of the communication complexity, given in [19].

There is a large literature also on preference learning (see e.g., [22] and the recent survey [24]), including the use of active learning [38, 2]. Preference learning focuses generally on learning the whole preference model, in contrast with learning an optimal alternative. Naturally, this can require many more queries, since much more information may need to be learnt. (An example which illustrates this contrast is the CP-nets formalism [13]. Consider a simple case where the dependency graph of an acyclic CP-net with n Boolean variables is known, but not the local orderings in each conditional preference table. To find an optimal alternative one needs just to ask a query for each variable in turn, i.e., n queries, starting with a variable with no parents. To learn the CP-net we need a query for each entry in the conditional preference table of each variable.)

Section 2 defines the basic concepts of preference families, questionnaires and query trees and gives a logarithmic lower bound of

their minimum sizes. In Section 3 we consider query languages based on whether an alternative is optimal or not; a more complex language of this kind achieves the logarithmic lower bound. Section 4 focuses on query languages using comparisons between alternatives, and gives a general upper bound on the number of required queries, and shows both this and the lower bound can be achieved by certain preference families. Section 5 uses notions of sufficient and necessary queries to give bounds on minimum questionnaire sizes, and these results are used in Section 6 for the very important case of families of linear preferences to characterise the minimum questionnaire size. Section 7 concludes.

2 The query formalisms

The formal framework is constructed in this section, defining preference families, queries, questionnaires and query trees.

2.1 Preference families

A *total pre-order* (or a *weak order*) \succsim on a finite set A of alternatives is a relation that is reflexive, transitive and complete (but might not be anti-symmetric). We write \succ for the strict part of \succsim , and \equiv for the symmetric part. Thus, $\alpha \succ \beta$ if and only if $\alpha \succsim \beta$ and $\beta \not\succsim \alpha$, and $\alpha \equiv \beta \iff \alpha \succsim \beta$ and $\beta \succsim \alpha$. Relation \equiv is an equivalence relation on A , and \succ is a strict total pre-order. For $B \subseteq A$, $O_{\succsim}(B)$ is the (always non-empty) set of optimal elements in B , i.e., for $\alpha \in A$, $\alpha \in O_{\succsim}(B) \iff \alpha \in B$ and for all $\beta \in B$, $\alpha \succsim \beta$.

A **preference family** \mathcal{P} on finite set of alternatives A (or an A -preference family) is defined to be a tuple $\mathcal{P} = \langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$, where W (sometimes notated as $W_{\mathcal{P}}$) is a labelling set (of arbitrary cardinality), and for each $w \in W$, \succ_w is a total pre-order on A . We use a preference family to model imprecise knowledge about a user's preference relation. For $B \subseteq A$, we abbreviate $O_{\succ_w}(B)$ to $O_w(B)$. For $\alpha \in A$ we define $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ to be all the user models $w \in W$ such that α is optimal (in A), i.e., $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \iff \alpha \in O_w(A)$.

Example 1. Let us define \mathcal{P}_1 by $A = \{a, b, c\}$. $W = \{u, v, w\}$, and their associated total pre-orders \succ_u, \succ_v and \succ_w by $a \equiv_w b \succ_w c$; $a \equiv_v c \succ_v b$; and $b \equiv_u c \succ_u a$. We have $O_v(\{a, b\}) = \{a\}$ and $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_1}(a) = \{v, w\}$.

2.2 Optimality cover and parameter $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$

Consider preference family $\mathcal{P} = \langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$. We say that a subset B of A is an *optimality cover* for \mathcal{P} [or a \mathcal{P} -*optimality cover*] if for every element w of W , some element of B is optimal with respect to \succ_w , i.e., $O_w(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$. Clearly A is always a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. In Example 1, $\{a, b\}$ is a \mathcal{P}_1 -optimality cover since in every user model in W , either a or b is optimal; similarly, $\{a, c\}$ and $\{b, c\}$. No singleton set is a \mathcal{P}_1 -optimality cover, since there is no alternative that is necessarily optimal, i.e., optimal with respect to each element of W .

The basic result below gives equivalent forms of the definition of a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover.

Proposition 1. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$ be a preference family, and let B be a non-empty subset of A . Then the following statements are all equivalent: (I) B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, i.e., for all $w \in W$, $O_w(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$; (II) for all $w \in W$, $O_w(B) = O_w(A) \cap B$; (III) $\bigcup_{\alpha \in B} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) = W$.

Proof: (I) \Rightarrow (II): Assume that B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, and consider any $w \in W$. (I) implies that there exists some $\alpha \in O_w(A) \cap B$. For any $\beta \in O_w(B) (\subseteq B)$ we have $\beta \succ_w \alpha$ because $\alpha \in B$ (and we have $\alpha \not\succeq_w \beta$ because $\beta \in A$), and so $\beta \in O_w(A)$, and thus, $O_w(B) \subseteq O_w(A) \cap B$. Also, any $\gamma \in O_w(A) \cap B$ is obviously optimal in B , showing that $\gamma \in O_w(A) \cap B \subseteq O_w(B)$, and hence, we have (II).

(II) \Rightarrow (I): Since B is finite and non-empty, $O_w(B)$ is non-empty, for all $w \in W$, and thus, by (II), $O_w(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$, showing that B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover.

(I) \Rightarrow (III): Assume that B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. By the definitions, $\bigcup_{\alpha \in B} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \subseteq W$. Now consider any $w \in W$. (I) implies that there exists $\alpha \in O_w(A) \cap B$ so $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \subseteq \bigcup_{\beta \in B} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$, showing (III).

(III) \Rightarrow (I): Consider any $w \in W$. (III) implies that there exists $\alpha \in B$ such that $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, i.e., $\alpha \in O_w(A) \cap B$, proving that B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. \square

Parameter $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ is defined to be the cardinality of a smallest \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, i.e., the minimum value of $|B|$ over all \mathcal{P} -optimality covers B . We say that such a subset B is a minimum-cardinality \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. Thus, $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_1) = 2$ in Example 1.

Example 2. We define a preference family \mathcal{P}_2 on set of alternatives $A = \{a, b, c, d\}$, and let $W = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$ with the four total pre-orders defined below.

$$\begin{array}{ll} a \succ_1 b \equiv_1 c \equiv_1 d. & b \succ_2 a \equiv_2 c \equiv_2 d. \\ c \succ_3 a \equiv_3 b \equiv_3 d. & d \succ_4 a \succ_4 b \equiv_4 c. \end{array}$$

A is the only \mathcal{P}_2 -optimality cover, and so $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_2) = 4$.

2.3 Preference statements

Given a set of alternatives A , a preference statement expresses a property of a total pre-order \succ on A .

For alternatives $\beta, \gamma \in A$ and $B \subseteq A$ we define the semantics of the preference statements $\beta \geq \gamma$, $\beta > \gamma$, $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ and $\text{Opt}(B)$ as follows, where \succ is a total pre-order on A :

- $\beta \geq \gamma$ holds for \succ if and only if $\beta \succ \gamma$.
- $\beta > \gamma$ holds for \succ if and only if $\beta \succ \gamma$; this holds if and only if $\gamma \not\succeq \beta$ does not hold.
- For $\beta \in A$: $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ holds for \succ if and only if $O_{\succ}(A) \ni \beta$. This is if and only if $\beta \geq \gamma$ holds for all $\gamma \in A$.
- For $B \subseteq A$: $\text{Opt}(B)$ holds for \succ if and only if $O_{\succ}(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$. This is if and only if $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ holds for some $\beta \in B$.
- For preference statement φ , we say that \succ satisfies $\neg\varphi$ if and only if it does not satisfy φ .

Preference statements for a preference family

Consider a preference family $\mathcal{P} = \langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$. For preference statement φ on A and $w \in W$ we say that w satisfies φ if the associated ordering relation \succ_w satisfies φ ; and we define $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{P}}$ to be the set of all $w \in W$ such that w satisfies φ ; hence we have $[\neg\varphi]_{\mathcal{P}} = W \setminus [\varphi]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Note that $[\text{Opt}(\beta)]_{\mathcal{P}} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$.

Given a set S of preference statements on A , and a preference family \mathcal{P} , we define $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} = \bigcap_{\varphi \in S} [\varphi]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and we say that S implies $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ given \mathcal{P} , if $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$, i.e., β is optimal for every w satisfying S , i.e., β is necessarily optimal given preference statements S . In Example 2, if $S = \{a > b, a > d\}$ then $[S]_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{w_1\}$ because w_1 is the only element of W satisfying those two statements.

Since a is optimal w.r.t. w_1 , i.e., $a \in O_{w_1}(A)$, we have that S implies $\text{Opt}(a)$ given \mathcal{P}_2 .

2.4 Queries and Query Languages

The fundamental task we are considering is to find an alternative that the agent orders best. To help with this we can ask queries. Here we only consider binary queries. A query involves a pair of preference statements (see Section 2.3), at least one of which must hold, where each preference statement expresses a property of the user's preference relation. Thus, a query on set of alternatives A is a (two element) set $Q = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$ of preference statements on A such that $[\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \cup [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} = W_{\mathcal{P}}$ for any preference family \mathcal{P} on A .

The user responds with an answer φ_i , where $i = 1$ or 2 , such that $[\varphi_i]_{\mathcal{P}}$ contains their user model w^* (so if $w^* \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \cap [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ then they could respond either φ_1 or φ_2).

Sometimes we abbreviate the query $Q = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$ to just one of its preference statements, φ_1 , when the context makes this unambiguous.

An *A-query language* is a query language relating to a set of alternatives A , i.e., based on preference statements built from A . We give two examples below, based on *comparison queries*; these are a very natural form of query, asking the user which of two alternatives they prefer.

Exclusive Comparison Query Language CompEx_A : For a set of alternatives A , we consider the language CompEx_A , which contains all pairs $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ over all $\alpha, \beta \in A$ with $\alpha \neq \beta$.

In Example 2, CompEx_A contains the query $\{a > b, b \geq a\}$, which splits W into two sets $[a > b]_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{w_1, w_4\}$ and $[b \geq a]_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{w_2, w_3\}$.

We also consider a different type of comparison query:

Symmetric Comparison Query Language CompSym_A : For set of alternatives A , the language CompSym_A contains all pairs $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ over all $\alpha, \beta \in A$ with $\alpha \neq \beta$.

2.5 Questionnaires

A questionnaire is a set of queries, given to the user simultaneously, such that user's answers to these queries will determine an optimal alternative for the user.

For an A -query language \mathcal{Q} and subset Γ of \mathcal{Q} of cardinality k , a *configuration* of Γ consists of k preference statements, one from each of the k queries. There are thus, 2^k configurations of Γ .

A configuration S of Γ is said to be *consistent* with respect to an A -preference family \mathcal{P} if there exists some $w \in W$ that satisfies each element of S , i.e., if $[S]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is non-empty.

A set of queries within a query language \mathcal{Q} is defined to be a *Q-questionnaire* for \mathcal{P} if for each consistent configuration S there exists some alternative $\gamma \in A$ such that S implies $\text{Opt}(\gamma)$ given \mathcal{P} , i.e., $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$. Hence, for any user with model $w \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$, their answers to the queries will determine an optimal alternative for them.

For preference family \mathcal{P} and query language \mathcal{Q} for set of alternatives A , the value $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ is defined to be the minimum cardinality of any \mathcal{Q} -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , i.e., the minimum questionnaire size. Hence, if $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) = K$ then it is possible to find a \mathcal{Q} -questionnaire of cardinality K whose answers will determine an optimal alternative for the user.

In Example 2, $MQS(\mathcal{P}_2; \text{CompEx}_A) = 3$ because a smallest CompEx_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} has three queries: for instance, Γ consisting of $\{a > b, b \geq a\}$, $\{a > d, d \geq a\}$ and $\{b > c, c \geq b\}$.

Only four of the eight configurations are consistent, and each of these imply that some alternative is optimal. For instance, the configuration $S = \{a > b, a > d, c \geq b\}$ implies $\text{Opt}(a)$ for \mathcal{P}_2 since $[S]_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{w_1\} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(a)$.

Figure 1. A CompEx_A -query tree \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P}_2 in Example 2, showing the preference statement associated with each edge, and the alternative α_λ associated with each leaf node λ . The root node has associated query $\{a > b, b \geq a\}$. The node below the edge labelled by $a > b$ is associated with the query $\{a > d, d \geq a\}$, with associated leaf nodes λ_1 and λ_2 with $\alpha_{\lambda_1} = a$ and $\alpha_{\lambda_2} = d$. The node below the $b \geq a$ edge has query $\{b > c, c \geq b\}$, with associated leaf nodes with $\alpha_{\lambda_3} = b$ and $\alpha_{\lambda_4} = c$.

2.6 Query trees and Depth

Questionnaires do not allow the queries to be dynamic, i.e., to be chosen based on the user's answers to earlier queries. We formalise a dynamic query strategy (or policy) with what we call a *query tree* (see Figure 1).

Given set of alternatives A , a query tree with respect to query language \mathcal{Q} , is a binary rooted tree (so it has at least one node), with edges directed away from the root. Associated with each non-leaf node σ is a query $Q_\sigma = \{\psi_1, \psi_2\} \in \mathcal{Q}$, and one of the two directed out-edges from σ is labelled with ψ_1 , and the other is labelled with ψ_2 . Each leaf node λ is associated with an alternative $\alpha_\lambda \in A$.

For preference family \mathcal{P} , a query tree \mathcal{T} is defined to be a \mathcal{Q} -query tree for \mathcal{P} if for every leaf node λ , the set S_λ , of preference statements on the edges from the root to λ , implies $\text{Opt}(\alpha_\lambda)$ for \mathcal{P} , i.e., if $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$, i.e., α_λ is optimal in A for any w that satisfies each statement in S_λ .

If we have a \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P} then, starting at the root node, we can ask the query at each non-leaf node we reach, where we follow the edge corresponding with the answer. When we reach a leaf node λ we have learned the preference statements S_λ , and from these we can deduce that alternative α_λ is optimal for the user. Thus, for any $w \in W$ there exists at least one leaf node λ such that $w \in [S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and so, $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$. Hence, if $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}$ is the set of leaf nodes of \mathcal{T} then $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda) = W$, which, by Proposition 1 form (III), implies that $\{\alpha_\lambda : \lambda \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}\}$ is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, and thus,

$$|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}). \quad (1)$$

Lemma 1. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$ be a preference family and let \mathcal{Q} be an A -query language. Suppose that \mathcal{T} is a \mathcal{Q} -query tree for \mathcal{P} , and let $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}$ be its set of leaf nodes. Then $\{\alpha_\lambda : \lambda \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}\}$ is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, and $|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P})$.

Proof: For every query $Q = \{\psi_1, \psi_2\} \in \mathcal{Q}$ and every $w \in W$, w satisfies either ψ_1 or ψ_2 . Hence for any $w \in W$ there exists some leaf node λ such that $w \in [S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and so, $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$. Hence, $\bigcup_{\lambda \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda) = W$, which, by Proposition 1 (form (III)), implies that $\{\alpha_\lambda : \lambda \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}\}$ is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. By definition of $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ we have $|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P})$. \square

The depth of a leaf node is defined to be the number of edges between it and the root node. We define $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$ to be largest depth of any leaf node in \mathcal{T} . For any sequence of user answers, the number of required queries is at most $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$. For \mathcal{T} in Figure 1, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = 2$ since there are at most 2 edges in each path from the root to a leaf node.

The depth of \mathcal{P} relative to the query language \mathcal{Q} , written as $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ is defined to be the minimum of $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$ over all \mathcal{Q} -query trees \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P} . For $K \geq 1$, if $K \geq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ then it is possible to guarantee to find an optimal alternative for the decision maker with K queries. If $K < \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ it is not possible to guarantee that.

For any \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P} the number $|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}|$ of leaf nodes is at most $2^{\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})}$, and so, $^1 \text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \lceil \log_2 |\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \rceil$. Hence, by Equation 1, we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$, and thus, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$.

Any questionnaire $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$ for preference family \mathcal{P} can be turned into a \mathcal{Q} -query tree with depth $|\Gamma|$, by choosing an arbitrary ordering Q_1, \dots, Q_m of Γ , and using the same ordering Q_1, \dots, Q_m of queries in each path from the root to any of the 2^m leaf nodes. Hence we have:

Proposition 2. Given a finite set A of alternatives, and any A -query language \mathcal{Q} and A -preference family \mathcal{P} we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$.

Proof: For any \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P} , the number $|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}|$ of leaf nodes is at most $2^{\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})}$, since it is a binary tree, and so we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \lceil \log_2 |\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \rceil$, because $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$ is an integer. Hence, by Equation 1 (or Lemma 1), we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$, and thus, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$.

Any questionnaire $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$ for preference family \mathcal{P} can be turned into a \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} with depth $|\Gamma|$, by choosing an arbitrary ordering Q_1, \dots, Q_m of Γ , and using the same ordering Q_1, \dots, Q_m of queries in each path from the root to any of the 2^m leaf nodes. For any leaf node λ , let S_λ be the associated set of answers to the queries on the path from the root to λ . If $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is non-empty then S_λ is a consistent configuration of Γ , and so, by the definition of a questionnaire, there exists $\gamma \in A$ such that $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, and we define $\alpha_\lambda = \gamma$ (for some such γ) and hence, the required condition for the leaf node λ holds: $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$. If $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is empty then we can choose α_λ to be any element of A , and then $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$ holds trivially. This shows that \mathcal{T} is a \mathcal{Q} -query tree for \mathcal{P} with depth $|\Gamma|$. Choosing Γ to be such that $|\Gamma| = MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ (which is possible by definition of $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$) we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$, which implies $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$, completing the proof. \square

With $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{P}_2$ in Example 2, by e.g., by Proposition 2 we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_2; \text{CompEx}_A) \geq 2 = \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}_2) \rceil$ since $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_2) = 4$. With query tree \mathcal{T} in Figure 1 we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = 2$. One can easily check that $[S_\lambda]_{\mathcal{P}_2} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_2}(\alpha_\lambda)$ holds for each leaf node λ , showing that \mathcal{T} is a CompEx_A -query tree for \mathcal{P}_2 ; for instance, since w_4 is the only user preference model in W such that both $a > b$ and $d \geq a$ hold, and d is (the unique alternative that is) optimal in A with respect to w_4 , we have that this pair of statements (on the path to the leaf node λ_2 associated with d) imply that d is optimal for \mathcal{P}_2 , and, in fact, $[S_{\lambda_2}]_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{a > b, d \geq a\}_{\mathcal{P}_2} = \{w_4\} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_2}(d) = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_2}(\alpha_{\lambda_2})$. Hence, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_2; \text{CompEx}_A) = 2$.

¹ For real number r , the value $\lceil r \rceil$ is the smallest integer n with $n \geq r$.

Chain query trees

Let \mathcal{Q} be an A -query language. We say that a \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} is a chain if for every body node (i.e., non-leaf node), at least one of its two children is a leaf node. In this case $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$ is one less than the number of leaf nodes, i.e., $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = |\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| - 1$. Using Equation 1 (or Lemma 1) we have the following result.

Lemma 2. *Given finite set A of alternatives, and any A -query language \mathcal{Q} and A -preference family \mathcal{P} , suppose that \mathcal{Q} -query tree \mathcal{T} is a chain. Then $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.*

Proof: The non-leaf nodes in a chain are linearly ordered by the parent-child relationship, beginning with the root node. There are $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$ non-leaf nodes, with the last one being such that both its child nodes are leaf nodes, and with all the others having one of its children being a leaf node. Thus, there are $|\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})| + 1$ leaf nodes, so $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = |\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| - 1$. By Equation 1 (or Lemma 1), $|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, and so $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. \square

2.7 Discussion of the sizes of the search spaces

We give some brief analysis regarding how large the search spaces are, for finding minimum cardinality questionnaires, and for finding minimum depth query trees.

Consider for instance the language CompEx_A , and let $n = |A|$. We might, for instance, be interested in problems with tens or hundreds of alternatives. There are $N = n(n-1)$ possible queries. The questionnaire size will typically be at least linear in n , so let us consider the number of questionnaires of cardinality n . This is $\binom{N}{n}$, which is greater than $(\frac{N}{n})^n$, and so the number of questionnaires is more than m^m where $m = n - 1$.

Now consider the query trees of depth K that have $2^K - 1$ non-leaf nodes. We have to choose a query for each non-leaf node, but let us avoid picking a query twice on the same path from the root to a leaf node; so we have more than $M = n(n-1) - K$ choices for each non-leaf node, and thus more than $(2^K - 1)^M$ query trees of this kind. Even if the depth K is as little as $\log_2 n$ (which would be the minimum possible depth if $n = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, see Proposition 2), we have $M > (n-1)^2$ so the number of such query trees would be at least $m^{(m^2)}$ where again $m = n - 1$. Even if $n = |A| = 7$ this is more than 10^{28} .

3 Query languages based on optimality

We consider here query languages involving queries that ask whether a particular alternative is optimal in Section 3.1, or whether one of a set of alternatives is optimal, in Section 3.2. With the latter rather complex query language we show that the logarithmic lower bound on Depth , given in Proposition 2, can be achieved for an arbitrary preference family, and a variation of it can also achieve the logarithmic lower bound on MQS .

3.1 Queries of optimality of singleton set

For set of alternatives A we define the query language $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ to consist of all queries $\{\text{Opt}(\gamma), \neg\text{Opt}(\gamma)\}$ over $\gamma \in A$. For a given A -preference family \mathcal{P} , this is interpreted as $\{[\text{Opt}(\gamma)]_{\mathcal{P}}, [\neg\text{Opt}(\gamma)]_{\mathcal{P}}\}$, where $[\text{Opt}(\gamma)]_{\mathcal{P}} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, and $[\neg\text{Opt}(\gamma)]_{\mathcal{P}} = W \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$. This query tests whether or not the alternative γ is optimal for the decision maker.

For any $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree for a preference family \mathcal{P} , we can turn any child node associated with a statement $\text{Opt}(\gamma)$ into a leaf

node λ with $\alpha_{\lambda} = \gamma$. In this way we generate a query tree that is a chain, i.e., for every non-leaf node, at least one of its child nodes is a leaf. For a chain \mathcal{T} , $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) = |\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}}| - 1$ and so, by Equation 1, any such query tree has depth at least $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, which implies $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.

Choose any \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, and use any labelling β_1, \dots, β_m of B . Let Γ be the set of queries based on $\text{Opt}(\beta_1), \dots, \text{Opt}(\beta_{m-1})$. Any configuration including a statement $\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$ obviously implies $\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$; the only other configuration includes $\neg\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$ for every $j = 1, \dots, m-1$, and, by Proposition 1 (form (III)), this implies $\text{Opt}(\beta_m)$ because B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. Hence, Γ is a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} of cardinality $m-1$, so $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \leq m-1 = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. Using Proposition 2 this implies:

Theorem 1. *For every preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A , $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.*

Proof: Consider any $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree \mathcal{T} for a preference family \mathcal{P} . We transform \mathcal{T} into another $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree \mathcal{T}' by turning any child node associated with a statement $\text{Opt}(\gamma)$ into a leaf node λ with $\alpha_{\lambda} = \gamma$. Clearly, \mathcal{T}' is also $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree \mathcal{T} for \mathcal{P} , and it is a chain, and so $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}') \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, by Lemma 2. Since \mathcal{T}' is a truncated version of \mathcal{T} we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}')$, and so $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. Since \mathcal{T} is an arbitrary $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree for \mathcal{P} , we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.

As described above, we choose any \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, and use any labelling β_1, \dots, β_m of B , and let Γ be the set of queries based on $\text{Opt}(\beta_1), \dots, \text{Opt}(\beta_{m-1})$. Any configuration including a statement $\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$ obviously implies $\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$; the only other configuration includes $\neg\text{Opt}(\beta_j)$ for every $j = 1, \dots, m-1$, and, by Proposition 1 (form (III)), this implies $\text{Opt}(\beta_m)$ because B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover. Hence, Γ is a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} of cardinality $m-1$, so $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \leq m-1 = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. Proposition 2 and the first paragraph of this proof imply that $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \geq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, and so we have $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. \square

3.2 Optimality of one of a set of alternatives

Let $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})$ consist of all queries $\{\text{Opt}(C), \neg\text{Opt}(C)\}$ over all $C \subseteq A$. For a given preference family \mathcal{P} , $\text{Opt}(C)$ is interpreted as $[\text{Opt}(C)]_{\mathcal{P}} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(C) = \bigcup_{\gamma \in C} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$.

By an iterative binary division of a minimum-cardinality \mathcal{P} -optimality set, it can be shown that this query language has the minimum possible query depth of $\log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P})$.

Theorem 2. *For every preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A , $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})) = \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$.*

Proof: Choose any \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B equivalent with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, and choose any labelling β_1, \dots, β_m of B . For clarity of notation we consider the case where m is a power of 2: $m = 2^q$. However, the more general case when $q = \lceil \log_2 m \rceil$ follows with essentially the same argument.

For $1 \leq s \leq t \leq m$, let us abbreviate the set $\{\beta_s, \dots, \beta_t\}$ to $C_{s,t}$, and the preference statement $\text{Opt}(C_{s,t})$ to $\text{Opt}(s, t)$, and the query $\{\text{Opt}(s, t), \neg\text{Opt}(s, t)\}$ to $Q(s, t)$. We say that the query $Q(s, t)$ and the associated preference statement $\text{Opt}(C_{s,t})$, have *width* r , where $r = t - s + 1 = |C_{s,t}|$.

We will define a $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})$ -query tree with the following properties. In any branch, after k queries (from the root), for $k = 0, \dots, q$, the answers to those queries imply a preference statement $\text{Opt}(s'_k, t'_k)$ of width 2^{q-k} . In particular, $s'_0 = 1$ and $t'_0 = m = 2^q$; the statement $\text{Opt}(s'_0, t'_0)$ (i.e., $\text{Opt}(B)$) holds for every $w \in W$, using Proposition 1 form (III), because B is an optimality cover for \mathcal{P} . Hence, after q queries (i.e., at depth q), we will be able to deduce a statement $\text{Opt}(C_{s,s})$ of width 1, i.e., a statement $\text{Opt}(\beta_s)$, and this is a leaf node of the query tree.

For $k \geq 1$, after the answers to $k - 1$ queries we will know a preference statement $\text{Opt}(s'_{k-1}, t'_{k-1})$, and will ask the query $Q(s_k, t_k)$ which has width 2^{q-k} , where $s_k = s'_{k-1}$ and $t_k = s'_{k-1} - 1 + 2^{q-k}$. In particular, the first query, associated with the root node, is $Q(s_1, t_1)$ where $s_1 = 1$ and $t_1 = 2^{q-1}$.

With user answer $\text{Opt}(s_k, t_k)$ (i.e., with the directed edge corresponding to that statement), we then know the statement $Q(s_k, t_k)$ which has width 2^{q-k} , and we set $s'_k = s_k$ and $t'_k = t_k$ (for the associated child node).

With the other answer, $\neg\text{Opt}(s_k, t_k)$, we can deduce the statement $Q(t_k + 1, t'_{k-1})$ (again, of width 2^{q-k}). This is because the pair of statements $Q(s_k, t'_k)$ and $\neg Q(s_k, t_k)$ imply some that element β_j is optimal with $j \in \{t_k + 1, \dots, t'_{k-1}\}$, and thus imply $Q(t_k + 1, t'_{k-1})$. We then set $s'_k = t_k + 1$ and $t'_k = t'_{k-1}$ (for the associated child node).

Hence, there exists a $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ -query tree for any \mathcal{P} with depth $q = \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$, which is the minimum possible, by Proposition 2. \square

Although the query language $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})$ generates the minimum possible depth, it does not in general generate the minimum possible questionnaire size, and in fact, there exists a preference family \mathcal{P} with $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}))$ as bad² as $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. So we focus in the next section on an even more complex query language that gives the logarithmic value of MQS for arbitrary preference families.

To see that there exists a preference family \mathcal{P} with $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}))$ as bad as $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, consider an arbitrary non-empty subset B of the set of alternatives A , and define W such that (I) for all $w \in W$ we have $O_w(A) \subseteq B$, and (II) for each non-empty subset C of B there exists $w \in W$ with $O_w(A) = C$. Let $m = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) = |B|$. For any $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})$ -questionnaire Γ for \mathcal{P} consider the configuration S containing all the positive answers, say, $\text{Opt}(C_1), \dots, \text{Opt}(C_t)$. Now, for this \mathcal{P} , we can eliminate elements in any C_i that are not in B , so we can assume without loss of generality that each $C_i \subseteq B$.

By definition of a questionnaire, S implies some statement of the form $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ (and $\beta \in B$, by the definition of \mathcal{P}). There exists $w \in W$ such that $O_w(A) = (\bigcup_{i=1}^t C_i) \setminus \{\beta\}$. Since w does not satisfy $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$, it does not satisfy S , so that there exists i such that w does not satisfy $\text{Opt}(C_i)$, which implies that $C_i = \{\beta\}$. We then relabel so that $i = t$.

Now consider the configuration S_2 consisting of $\text{Opt}(C_1), \dots, \text{Opt}(C_{t-1}), \neg\text{Opt}(\beta)$. For \mathcal{P} this is equivalent to removing β from each of the sets C_i , to form set $C'_i = C_i \setminus \{\beta\}$, and removing β from B . Then S_2 implies $\text{Opt}(\beta')$ for some $\beta' \in B$, and so, $\{\text{Opt}(C'_1), \dots, \text{Opt}(C'_{t-1})\}$ implies $\text{Opt}(\beta')$. Using the same reasoning as in the last paragraph, this only happens if some C'_i equals $\{\beta'\}$. Continuing, after $m - 1$ steps we eventually reduce B

² This is the worst possible, because of Theorem 1 and the fact that for any \mathcal{P} , $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt}))$ since $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})$ contains queries equivalent with those in $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$.

to a singleton set, and $|\Gamma| = t \geq m - 1 = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, showing that for this preference family \mathcal{P} we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. Hence, $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$ using Theorem 1 and the fact that for any \mathcal{P} , $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt})) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt}))$.

3.3 Ordered set optimality language

We label the alternatives in A as $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$; we use this ordering for tie-breaking. Consider any non-empty $B \subseteq A$, and let us write B as $\{\beta_0, \dots, \beta_{m-1}\}$, with the labelling being based on the labelling of A , i.e., if $\beta_i = \alpha_g$ and $\beta_j = \alpha_h$ then $i < j \iff g < h$. Let us define $\max_w(B)$ to mean the element β_j in $O_w(B)$ with the smallest index j .

For any $C \subseteq B$ we consider the preference statement $\text{Opt}'_B(C)$, with the language $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')$ consisting of all queries of the form $\{\text{Opt}'_B(C), \neg\text{Opt}'_B(C)\}$. The semantics of this statement is as follows.

For any \mathcal{P} , $[\text{Opt}'_B(C)]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is all $w \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$ such that $\max_w(B) \in C$, i.e., $w \in [\text{Opt}'_B(C)]_{\mathcal{P}}$ if and only if, among elements which are best within B according to ordering \succ_w , the first one (according to the tie-breaking ordering) is in C .

Consider any preference family \mathcal{P} on A , and let B be a cardinality-minimal \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, i.e., such that $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(B) = W_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$. As above, write B as $\{\beta_0, \dots, \beta_{m-1}\}$, with the labelling being based on the labelling of A .

Let $q = \lceil \log_2 m \rceil$, i.e., the smallest whole number greater or equal to $\log_2 m$. For each $j \in \{0, \dots, m - 1\}$, and for each $i = 1, \dots, q$, let $b_j(i)$ be the i^{th} digit in the binary representation of j , using the full q digits. For $i = 1, \dots, q$, define the set B_i to be the set of all β_j such that $b_j(i) = 1$.

We consider the set of queries Γ based on $\text{Opt}'_B(B_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, q$. Note that the statement $\neg\text{Opt}'_B(B_i)$ is equivalent to $\text{Opt}'_B(B \setminus B_i)$. It can be shown that this is a $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')$ -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and it is, by Proposition 2, of the minimum possible cardinality, i.e., $\lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$, which leads to the following result.

Lemma 3. For preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A , $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')) = \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$.

Proof: We will show that Γ is a $\mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')$ -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . For $w \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$ let $j(w)$ be defined to be the element $j \in \{0, \dots, m - 1\}$ such that $\beta_j = \max_w(B)$, and so, $\beta_j \in O_w(B)$. Since B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover, Proposition 1 (form (II)), implies that $\beta_{j(w)}$ is optimal in A with respect to \succ_w , i.e., w satisfies $\text{Opt}(\beta_{j(w)})$.

Now, w satisfies the statement $\text{Opt}'_B(B_i)$ if and only if $\max_w(B) \in B_i$ if and only if $\beta_{j(w)} \in B_i$ if and only if the i^{th} binary digit of $j(w)$ is equal to 1.

Consider the answers set (configuration) S to Γ that is satisfied by w . Thus S determines each binary digit of $j(w)$ and hence determines $j(w)$, so that if w' also satisfies S then $j(w') = j(w)$, which we can write as $j(S)$. So, for any $v \in [S]_{\mathcal{P}}$ we have $\max_v(B) = \beta_{j(S)}$, and thus, v satisfies $\text{Opt}(\beta_{j(S)})$, showing that $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta_{j(S)})$. This proves that Γ is a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and we have $|\Gamma| = q = \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$, implying that $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}_A^{\vee}(\text{Opt}')) \leq \lceil \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}) \rceil$. Combining this with Proposition 2 gives the theorem. \square

4 Bounds for comparison languages

We construct in Section 4.1 a general form of query tree that gives a general upper bound $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$ for *Depth* for comparison query languages, and we show in Section 4.2 that this is achieved for *approval preference families*, as defined below. A special kind of preference family consisting of lexicographic orders is shown in Section 4.3 to achieve the logarithmic lower bound for both *Depth* and minimum questionnaire size *MQS* (with a construction closely related to that used in the language $\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt}')$ mentioned in Section 3.2).

For node σ of a query tree we define S_σ to be the set of preference statements on the edges from the root to σ , and, given preference family \mathcal{P} , define W_σ to be the associated subset $[S_\sigma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ of $W_{\mathcal{P}}$, i.e., the set of all $w \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$ that satisfy S_σ .

For set of alternatives A , and any preference family \mathcal{P} on A and a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} , we can generate a CompEx_A -query tree with corresponding nodes and leaf node labelling by replacing each query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ by the query $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$. A similar point applies for questionnaires, and so we have:

Proposition 3. *Consider any A -preference family \mathcal{P} . Then, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$, and $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$.*

Proof: Let \mathcal{T} be a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} , and \mathcal{T}' be the associated CompEx_A -query tree with corresponding nodes and leaf node labelling by replacing each query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ by the query $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$.

For node σ , let W_σ be the associated subset of W for the CompSym_A -query tree, and let W'_σ be the associated subset of W for the CompEx_A -query tree. Then $W'_\sigma \subseteq W_\sigma$, and so, in particular, for any leaf node λ , we have $W'_\lambda \subseteq W_\lambda \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$. Hence, \mathcal{T}' is a CompEx_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} with the same depth as \mathcal{T} . This proves that the depth of a preference family with respect to CompEx_A is no more than the depth of the preference family with respect to CompSym_A , and thus, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$. A similar argument also applies to questionnaires, so $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$. \square

4.1 A general upper bound for Depth

Using a subset B of alternatives we will define a query tree of depth $|B| - 1$ that is a CompSym_A -query tree for preference family \mathcal{P} if and only if B is an optimality cover for \mathcal{P} . This leads to an upper bound of $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$ for $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$.

Winner-Stays-On query tree for comparison queries (CompSym_A): For any A and preference family \mathcal{P} for A , non-empty subset B of A , and labelling β_1, \dots, β_m for B , we define a query tree such that

(I) with the root node (which we call level 0 of the tree) we associate the query $\{\beta_1 \geq \beta_2, \beta_2 \geq \beta_1\}$.

(II) To every node at level k with $1 \leq k < m$, with parent edge labelled with $\beta_i \geq \beta_j$ ($\max(i, j) = k + 1$), we associate the query $\{\beta_i \geq \beta_{k+2}, \beta_{k+2} \geq \beta_i\}$.

(III) For a leaf node λ , at level $m - 1$, with parent edge labelled with $\beta_i \geq \beta_j$ ($\max(i, j) = m$), we let α_λ be β_i .

We call this query tree $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$; it has depth $m - 1$.

For an A -preference family \mathcal{P} , there exists some \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B such that $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$ (by definition of the latter). Label B as $\{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$. Consider any leaf node λ in the CompSym_A -query tree $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$, and then $\alpha_\lambda = \beta_i$ for some $\beta_i \in B$.

If w satisfies the set of preference statements S_λ (on the edges from the root to the leaf λ) then it follows that $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_j$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, and so $\beta_i \in \text{O}_w(B)$. Proposition 1 (form (II)) implies that $\beta_i \in \text{O}_w(A)$ and so $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta_i)$. This shows that $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$ is a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} with depth $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.

This argument is proved formally with the results below.

Lemma 4. *Let A be a set of alternatives, and for $m \geq 1$ let β_1, \dots, β_m be a sequence of different elements of A , and let $B = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$. Let \mathcal{P} be any preference family on A . Consider any node σ of the query tree $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$, and its associated set S_σ of statements on the edges from the root to σ , and let $\beta_i \geq \beta_j$ be the preference statement associated with the parent edge of σ . If $w \in [S_\sigma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ then $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_k$ for all $1 \leq k \leq \max(i, j)$.*

Proof: We will prove this by induction on $h = \max(i, j)$, with $2 \leq h \leq m$. It is clearly true for $h = 2$. Now assume that it is true for $h = g - 1 < m$, and we will prove that it holds for $h = g$. There are two cases: (a) $i < j$ or (b) $i > j$. In both cases we have $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_j$ because of the statement $\beta_i \geq \beta_j$ in S_σ .

If (a) then $h = g = j$, and the inductive hypothesis implies $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_k$ for all $k \leq g - 1$, and we also have $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_j$, so we have $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_k$ for all $1 \leq k \leq g$.

If (b) then $h = g = i$ and the inductive hypothesis implies $\beta_j \succ_w \beta_k$ for all $k \leq g - 1$, and we also have $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_j$, so we have $\beta_i \succ_w \beta_k$ for all $k \leq g$. This completes the inductive argument. \square

Lemma 5. *Let A be a set of alternatives, and for $m \geq 1$ let β_1, \dots, β_m be a sequence of different elements of A , and let $B = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$. Then the following both hold.*

- (i) $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)) = |B| - 1$;
- (ii) Let \mathcal{P} be a preference family on set of alternatives A . Then $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$ is a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} if and only if B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover.
- (iii) There exists a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} with depth $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.

Proof: Clearly, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)) = |B| - 1$. Regarding (ii): If \mathcal{L} is its set of leaf nodes then $\{\alpha_\lambda : \lambda \in \mathcal{L}\}$ is equal to B . Hence, if $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$ is a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} then B is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover by Lemma 1, since B is the set of alternatives associated with leaf nodes of $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$.

Regarding the converse: applying Lemma 4 to any leaf node λ , with associated set of preference statements S_λ , shows that for all w satisfying S_λ and all $\beta_j \in B$ we have $\alpha_\lambda \succ_w \beta_j$, and thus, $\alpha_\lambda \in \text{O}_w(B)$ (since $\alpha_\lambda \in B$), so Proposition 1 (form (II)) implies $\alpha_\lambda \in \text{O}_w(A)$, and thus, $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$. We have shown that S_λ implies $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_\lambda)$ for \mathcal{P} , and so, $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$ is a query tree for \mathcal{P} .

(iii): By definition of $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ there exists a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$, and let us write $B = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$. Parts (i) and (ii) imply that $\mathcal{T}^{wso}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)$ is a CompSym_A -query tree for \mathcal{P} with depth $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. \square

Hence, using Proposition 3, we have

Proposition 4. *For every A -preference family \mathcal{P} we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.*

Proof: Proposition 3 implies $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$ and Lemma 5(iii) implies that $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$. \square

4.2 Achieving the upper bound on Depth

We define an approval ordering on A to be a total pre-order \succsim that only has two levels (equivalence classes), so that $\alpha \equiv \beta$ (i.e., $\alpha \succsim \beta \succsim \alpha$) for all $\alpha, \beta \in A \setminus O_{\succsim}(A)$. Equivalently, these are the total pre-orders \succsim such that for all $\alpha, \beta \in A$, if $\beta \succ \alpha$ then $\beta \in O_{\succsim}(A)$.

Consider any CompEx_A -query tree \mathcal{T} for approval family \mathcal{P}_a , i.e., a preference family $\langle A, W, \{\succsim_w : w \in W\} \rangle$ such that each of the preference relations \succsim_w is an approval ordering on A . The statement $\beta > \alpha$ implies $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ given \mathcal{P}_a , i.e., $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}_a} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_a}(\beta)$. Thus, any child node σ from an edge associated with a strict statement of the form $\beta > \alpha$ can be replaced by a leaf node λ with associated alternative $\alpha_\lambda = \beta$, and we still have a CompEx_A -query tree for \mathcal{P}_a . If we do this for all such nodes then we obtain a chain \mathcal{T}' with $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}') \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$.

As in the argument in Section 3.1, since \mathcal{T}' is a chain we have $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}') = |\mathcal{L}'_{\mathcal{T}}| - 1 \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$, using Equation 1, and so $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$. Since \mathcal{T} is an arbitrary CompEx_A -query tree, this implies $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$. Proposition 4 then implies that any approval preference family \mathcal{P}_a has the worst possible depth for the two comparison query languages.

Theorem 3. *Let \mathcal{P}_a be any approval preference family on set of alternatives A . Then $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$.*

Proof: Consider any CompEx_A -query tree \mathcal{T} for approval family $\mathcal{P}_a = \langle A, W, \{\succsim_w : w \in W\} \rangle$, so that each of the preference relations \succsim_w is an approval ordering on A . Since \succsim_w is an approval ordering, if $\beta \succ_w \alpha$ then $\beta \in O_w(A)$. Hence, the statement $\beta > \alpha$ implies $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ given \mathcal{P}_a , i.e., $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}_a} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}_a}(\beta)$. Thus, any child node σ from an edge associated with a strict statement of the form $\beta > \alpha$ can be replaced by a leaf node λ with associated alternative $\alpha_\lambda = \beta$, and we still have a CompEx_A -query tree for \mathcal{P}_a . If we do this for all such nodes then we obtain a chain \mathcal{T}' with $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}') \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{T})$, and thus, by Lemma 2, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{T}') \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$. Hence, any such query tree \mathcal{T} has depth at least $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, which implies $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) \geq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$. Proposition 4 then implies $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$, and therefore, $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$. \square

In fact, we also have $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$ for any approval family \mathcal{P}_a , using the questionnaire Γ_α consisting of queries $\beta > \alpha$ for each $\beta \in B \setminus \{\alpha\}$, where α is in a minimum-cardinality \mathcal{P}_a -optimality cover B .

To see this, notice that any consistent configuration of Γ_α that includes a statement $\beta > \alpha$ implies $\text{Opt}(\beta)$ for \mathcal{P}_a , since \mathcal{P}_a is an approval family. The only other consistent configuration of Γ includes all statements $\alpha \geq \beta$ for each $\beta \in B \setminus \{\alpha\}$. These imply $\text{Opt}(\alpha)$, because at least one element in B is optimal, and so α is optimal (see also Proposition 1, form (II)). Hence, Γ_α is a CompEx_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P}_a . The cardinality of this questionnaire is $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$, which equals $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A)$ by Theorem 3, and so $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A)$ is no more than this. Hence, by Proposition 2, $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$ for any approval preference family.

4.3 A lexicographic preference family

Let $A = W = \{0, 1\}^q$. Let $w \in W$. For different alternatives $\alpha, \beta \in A = \{0, 1\}^q$, let $j(\alpha, \beta)$ be the smallest $i \in \{1, \dots, q\}$

such that $\alpha(i) \neq \beta(i)$. We define \succ_w to be a total order such that $\alpha \succ_w \beta$ if and only if $\alpha(j(\alpha, \beta)) = w(j(\alpha, \beta))$. Define \mathcal{P}_{lex} to be $\langle A, W, \{\succ_w : w \in W\} \rangle$.

For $w \in W$ let α_w be the corresponding alternative, i.e., $\alpha_w = w$, i.e., for each $i = 1, \dots, q$, $\alpha_w(i) = w(i)$. Then $O_w(A) = \{\alpha_w\}$. Since any element of A can be uniquely optimal, the only optimality cover for \mathcal{P}_{lex} is A , and thus, $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_{lex}) = |A| = 2^q$.

Let γ^i and δ^i be any pair of alternatives in A that differ on the i^{th} Boolean variable but agree on all earlier ones, i.e., such that $\gamma^i(i) \neq \delta^i(i)$ and for all $j < i$ we have $\gamma^i(j) = \delta^i(j)$. Let Γ be the set of CompSym_A queries $\{\gamma^i \geq \delta^i : i = 1, \dots, q\}$, so that $|\Gamma| = q$. The answer to the i^{th} query determines the i^{th} component of w , so any collection of answers to these q queries determines a unique w , and the answers imply $\text{Opt}(\alpha_w)$. Γ is thus a questionnaire for \mathcal{P}_{lex} , and so, $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}_{lex}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq q = \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}_{lex})$. Hence, by Proposition 2, $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}_{lex}; \text{CompSym}_A) = \text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}_{lex}; \text{CompSym}_A) = \log_2 \kappa(\mathcal{P}_{lex})$. Therefore, preference family $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{P}_{lex}$ achieves the logarithmic lower bound from Proposition 2 for both $\text{Depth}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$ and minimum questionnaire size $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$, showing that this lower bound cannot be increased (for general \mathcal{P}).

In fact the same idea works for arbitrary $A = W \subseteq \{0, 1\}^q$ such that $|A| > 2^{q-1}$ (so that $\lceil \log_2 |A| \rceil = q$) and containing the zero vector and the q unit vectors.

For each i we can define γ^i to be the zero vector $\mathbf{0}$ and δ^i to be the unit vector $(0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$ differing with $\mathbf{0}$ only on the i^{th} component.

5 α -sufficient sets, and necessary queries

We will show that one can generate a questionnaire from certain kinds of query, and that any questionnaire for a preference family must include other kinds of query, which leads to bounds and characterisations of MQS that we use for linear preference families in Section 6, and for showing the worst possible values of minimum questionnaire size MQS in Proposition 7.

5.1 Sufficient conditions for questionnaires

Given preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A and $\alpha \in A$ and $D \subseteq A \setminus \{\alpha\}$, we say that D is an α -sufficient set if for α to be optimal in A it is sufficient for it to be optimal in $D \cup \{\alpha\}$, i.e., $\text{Opt}(\alpha)$ holds if and only if for every $\beta \in D$ the statement $\alpha \geq \beta$ holds; (that is, $[\text{Opt}(\alpha)]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\{\alpha \geq \beta : \beta \in D\}]_{\mathcal{P}}$). This notion leads to a method for generating CompSym_A questionnaires for \mathcal{P} .

Proposition 5. *Given preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A . Suppose that non-empty $B \subseteq A$ is such that for all $\alpha \in B$ there exists an α -sufficient set D_α that is a subset of B . Consider the set Γ of queries $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ over all $\alpha \in B$ and $\beta \in D_\alpha$. Then Γ is a CompSym_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} .*

In particular, for arbitrary preference family \mathcal{P} , we can choose a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$; and for $\alpha \in B$ let $D_\alpha = B \setminus \{\alpha\}$. Proposition 1 (form (II)) implies that D_α is an α -sufficient set. Proposition 5 implies that the generated set Γ is a CompSym_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and so $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq |\Gamma| = \frac{1}{2} \kappa(\mathcal{P})(\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1)$.

Proof of Proposition 5: Consider an arbitrary $w' \in W$, along with any compatible set of answers S from w' for the set of queries Γ (so that $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \ni w'$). It is sufficient to show that there exists $\alpha \in A$ such that S implies $\text{Opt}(\alpha)$ with respect to \mathcal{P} .

S consists of a set of elements of the form $\beta \geq \gamma$, where $\beta, \gamma \in B$, and so can be viewed as a binary relation on B . Let S^* be the reflexive and transitive closure of the binary relation S , which is therefore a pre-order. Let T be any top-cycle of S^* ; this is a set of elements that (I) are all equivalent with respect to the pre-order S^* , i.e., for all $\beta, \gamma \in T$ we have both $\beta \geq \gamma$ and $\gamma \geq \beta$ in S^* , and (II) if $\gamma \in T$ and $\beta \in B$ and $\beta \geq \gamma$ is in S^* then $\beta \in T$. Because B is finite there always exists a top-cycle (it could be a singleton set).

Consider any $\alpha \in T$. Then by (I) S^* contains $\alpha \geq \beta$ for each $\beta \in T$. In particular, this holds if $\beta \in D_\alpha \cap T$. Now consider any $\beta \in D_\alpha \setminus T$. By its definition, Γ contains the query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$, and so S contains either $\beta \geq \alpha$ or $\alpha \geq \beta$. But by (II), S^* does not contain $\beta \geq \alpha$, and so, S does not contain $\beta \geq \alpha$, and so it contains $\alpha \geq \beta$. Thus, S^* contains $\alpha \geq \beta$. We have shown that S^* contains $\alpha \geq \beta$ for all $\beta \in D_\alpha$.

Consider any w that is consistent with the answers S . Then \succ_w contains all pairs in S and, since \succ_w is transitive, it contains all pairs in S^* . Hence, $\alpha \succ_w \beta$ holds for each $\beta \in D_\alpha$, and thus, because D_α is an α -sufficient set, we have $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$. Hence the answers set S implies $\text{Opt}(\alpha)$ with respect to \mathcal{P} (i.e., $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$) proving that the set Γ of queries forms a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . \square

5.2 Necessary queries

Consider a query language \mathcal{Q} for preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives \mathcal{A} . For a query $Q = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$ in \mathcal{Q} , and $w_1, w_2 \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$, we say that Q divides w_1 and w_2 if either

- (I) $w_1 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$; or
- (II) $w_2 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_1 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Let us define \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} to be all queries in \mathcal{Q} that divide w_1 and w_2 ; these are the set of queries for which w_1 and w_2 must give different answers. If $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$ then any questionnaire Γ for \mathcal{P} must contain some element of \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} ; otherwise, there exists some set of answers (configuration) S to Γ and $\gamma \in A$ with $w_1, w_2 \in [S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, implying the contradiction $\gamma \in O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$. So we have:

Proposition 6. Consider a query language \mathcal{Q} for preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives \mathcal{A} . Let $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$ be a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . Then $\Gamma \cap \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} \neq \emptyset$ for every pair $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$.

Proof: Consider any elements $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$. We will prove that $\Gamma \cap \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} \neq \emptyset$.

For $k = 1, 2$, let S_k be a valid set of answers to Γ for w_k such that wherever it is possible to do so, we choose the same answer for w_1 as for w_2 . Hence, we only give a different answer to a query $Q \in \Gamma$ if Q divides w_1 and w_2 .

In more detail, we can define which preference statement of a query that S_1 and S_2 is chosen to contain in the following way. Writing $Q = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$, let us define that

- (i) if $w_1, w_2 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ we include φ_1 in both S_1 and S_2 ;
- (ii) else if $w_1, w_2 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ we include φ_2 in both S_1 and S_2 ;
- (iii) else if $w_1 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ then (since case (i) does not hold) $w_2 \notin [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$, so by the definition of a query we have $w_2 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and so $w_1 \notin [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ (since case (ii) does not hold) and thus, $w_1 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and we have to include φ_1 in S_1 and φ_2 in S_2 ;

- (iv) else if $w_1 \notin [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ then $w_1 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \notin [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$, so $w_2 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$; thus, $w_1 \in [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \in [\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \setminus [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and we have to put φ_2 in S_1 and φ_1 in S_2 .

Hence, the only cases when S_1 and S_2 contain a different answer to query Q are case (iii) when condition (I) holds, and case (iv) when condition (II) holds; in either of these two cases we have that Q divides w_1 and w_2 .

Thus, if $S_1 \neq S_2$ then Γ contains a query Q that divides w_1 and w_2 , i.e., $\Gamma \cap \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} \neq \emptyset$. Hence, it is sufficient to show that $S_1 \neq S_2$.

We proceed using *Proof by Contradiction*. Suppose $S_1 = S_2$. By definition of S_1 and S_2 we have $w_1 \in [S_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \in [S_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and so $w_2 \in [S_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$. By the definition of a questionnaire there exists $\alpha_1 \in A$ such that $[S_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_1)$. Then, $w_1, w_2 \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha_1)$ and so $\alpha_1 \in O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A)$ contradicting the assumption that the latter set is empty. \square

Achieving the upper bound on minimum questionnaire size

For any set of alternatives A consider any non-empty subset B . We construct a particular A -preference family \mathcal{P}' as follows. Let W consist of an element $w(\alpha, \beta)$ for each $\alpha \in B$ and different $\beta \in B$. Their orderings over A are chosen in any way such that, for all different $\alpha, \beta \in B$, (I) for all $\gamma \in A \setminus \{\alpha, \beta\}$, $\alpha \succ_{w(\alpha, \beta)} \beta \succ_{w(\alpha, \beta)} \gamma$, and (II) orderings $\succ_{w(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $\succ_{w(\beta, \alpha)}$ are the same on $A \setminus \{\alpha, \beta\}$ (so that they only differ on which of α and β is optimal). Then $\kappa(\mathcal{P}') = |B|$.

There are only two queries in CompEx_A that divide $w(\alpha, \beta)$ and $w(\beta, \alpha)$, i.e., $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ and the query $\{\beta > \alpha, \alpha \geq \beta\}$. Hence, by Proposition 6, any CompEx_A -questionnaire Γ needs, for each different pair of alternatives $\alpha, \beta \in B$, to contain either the query $\alpha > \beta$ or the query $\beta > \alpha$, and thus, $|\Gamma| \geq \frac{1}{2}|B|(|B| - 1)$, which shows that $MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompEx}_A) \geq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}')(\kappa(\mathcal{P}') - 1)$ for this preference family \mathcal{P}' . Hence using Proposition 3 and the argument after Proposition 5, we have:

Proposition 7. For any \mathcal{P} we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P})(\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1)$. For any set of alternatives A and any non-empty subset B of A there exists an A -preference family \mathcal{P}' such that B is a minimum cardinality \mathcal{P}' -optimality cover and $MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompEx}_A) = MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompSym}_A) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}')(\kappa(\mathcal{P}') - 1)$.

Proof: Consider first any A -preference family \mathcal{P} . By Proposition 3, $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A)$. As discussed in the paragraph after and the argument after Proposition 5, we can choose a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B with $|B| = \kappa(\mathcal{P})$; and for $\alpha \in B$ let $D_\alpha = B \setminus \{\alpha\}$, which, by Proposition 1 (form (II)) implies that D_α is an α -sufficient set. Let Γ be the set of queries $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ over all $\alpha \in B$ and $\beta \in B \setminus \{\alpha\}$. Proposition 5 implies that Γ is a CompSym_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and so $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) \leq |\Gamma| = \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P})(\kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1)$.

We now consider the preference family \mathcal{P}' defined before the proposition, which is such that $\kappa(\mathcal{P}') = |B|$. For each different α and β in B there are only two queries in CompEx_A that divide $w(\alpha, \beta)$ and $w(\beta, \alpha)$, i.e., $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ and the query $\{\beta > \alpha, \alpha \geq \beta\}$. Hence, by Proposition 6, any CompEx_A -questionnaire Γ needs to contain either the query $\alpha > \beta$ or the query $\beta > \alpha$, and thus, $|\Gamma| \geq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}')(\kappa(\mathcal{P}') - 1)$, which shows that $MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompEx}_A) \geq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}')(\kappa(\mathcal{P}') - 1)$. The

first part of the proposition then implies $MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompEx}_A) = MQS(\mathcal{P}'; \text{CompSym}_A) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}')(\kappa(\mathcal{P}') - 1)$. \square

The above construction can be modified to show that there exists an approval preference family \mathcal{P}_a with $MQS(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A) = \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a)(\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1)$, so this illustrates the fact that $MQS(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A)$ can sometimes be much larger than $MQS(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompEx}_A)$, which equals $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1$ for approval families \mathcal{P}_a (see the remark after Theorem 3).

For any non-empty $B \subseteq A$, we define $W_{\mathcal{P}_a}$ to contain w_α for all $\alpha \in B$, where \succ_{w_α} is the approval ordering such that $O_{w_\alpha}(A) = \{\alpha\}$. Then B is a minimum-cardinality \mathcal{P}_a -optimality cover, so $\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) = |B|$. For different $\alpha, \beta \in B$, the only CompSym_A query $\{\gamma \geq \delta, \delta \geq \gamma\}$ that divides w_α and w_β has $\gamma \succ_{w_\alpha} \delta$ and $\delta \succ_{w_\beta} \gamma$ and thus, $\gamma = \alpha$ and $\delta = \beta$. Hence, by Proposition 6, any CompSym_A -questionnaire Γ for \mathcal{P}_a needs to contain the query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$, and thus, for this approval family \mathcal{P}_a , $|\Gamma| \geq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a)(\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1)$, which shows that $MQS(\mathcal{P}_a; \text{CompSym}_A) \geq \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a)(\kappa(\mathcal{P}_a) - 1)$, with the argument after Proposition 5, implying equality.

Equivalence of queries: Consider a query language \mathcal{Q} for preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives \mathcal{A} . Queries $Q = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$ and $Q' = \{\varphi'_1, \varphi'_2\}$ in \mathcal{Q} are said to be equivalent for preference family \mathcal{P} if $\{[\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}}, [\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}}\}$ equals $\{[\varphi'_1]_{\mathcal{P}}, [\varphi'_2]_{\mathcal{P}}\}$, i.e., if either (i) $[\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\varphi'_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\varphi'_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$, or (ii) $[\varphi_1]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\varphi'_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\varphi_2]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\varphi'_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

We also write this as \mathcal{P} -equivalence; it is an equivalence relation on \mathcal{Q} . If two queries are equivalent for \mathcal{P} we can always replace one by the other, and we never need both of them.

We give a basic lemma for questionnaires regarding equivalences.

Lemma 6. *For query language \mathcal{Q}_A and preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives A , suppose that Γ_1 is a \mathcal{Q}_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and suppose that $\Gamma_2 \subseteq \mathcal{Q}_A$ is such that for every element $Q \in \Gamma_1$ there exists $Q' \in \Gamma_2$ such that Q and Q' are \mathcal{P} -equivalent. Then Γ_2 is a \mathcal{Q}_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} .*

Proof: Consider any consistent configuration S' for Γ_2 (given \mathcal{P}), so that $[S']_{\mathcal{P}} \neq \emptyset$. We will show that there exists $\gamma \in A$ such that $[S']_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, proving that Γ_2 is a questionnaire.

For each query $Q \in \Gamma_1$ there exists some $Q' \in \Gamma_2$ such that Q and Q' are \mathcal{P} -equivalent. One of the answers $\varphi_{Q'}$ of Q' is in the configuration S' , and, by the \mathcal{P} -equivalence of Q and Q' , there exists φ_Q that is one of the two parts of Q such that $[\varphi_Q]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\varphi_{Q'}]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Let S equal $\{\varphi_Q : Q \in \Gamma_1\}$, which is thus a configuration for Γ_1 . Then, $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} = \bigcap_{Q \in \Gamma_1} [\varphi_Q]_{\mathcal{P}} = \bigcap_{Q \in \Gamma_1} [\varphi_{Q'}]_{\mathcal{P}} \supseteq [S']_{\mathcal{P}}$, because each $\varphi_{Q'}$ is in S' , and so we have $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \supseteq [S']_{\mathcal{P}} \neq \emptyset$, showing that S is a consistent \mathcal{P} -configuration. Since Γ_1 is a questionnaire, there exists $\gamma \in A$ such that $[S]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, and thus we have $[S']_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, as required. \square

In particular, Lemma 6 implies that any superset of a \mathcal{Q}_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} is a \mathcal{Q}_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} .

Simple necessary queries: Consider a query language \mathcal{Q} for preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives \mathcal{A} , and a query $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$. Then Q is defined to be a *simple necessary query for \mathcal{P}* (written $Q \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P})$) if there exists $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that (I) $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$, and (II) $Q \in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2}$, and any two queries in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} are \mathcal{P} -equivalent.

If a query divides w_1 and w_2 then any equivalent query also divides w_1 and w_2 . Hence, if a query is in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} then so is every equivalent query. Thus, if Q is a simple necessary query for \mathcal{P} then so is every equivalent query.

Let $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P})$ be the set of all simple necessary queries in \mathcal{Q} . Equivalence of queries is an equivalence relation, in particular, on $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P})$.

A *simple necessary equivalence class* is a \mathcal{P} -equivalence class in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P})$. C is a simple necessary equivalence class if and only if any two queries in C are equivalent and there exists $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that (I) $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$, and (II) $C = \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2}$.

Let Γ be a set of queries. We say that a subset $\Gamma' \subseteq \Gamma$ is an *equivalence-reduced version of Γ* , if (I) for every query in Γ there exists a query in Γ' that is equivalent for \mathcal{P} ; and (II) no pair of queries in Γ' are equivalent for \mathcal{P} .

Simple necessary queries lead to a lower bound for $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$, and can sometimes even determine it, as shown by the following result, which is used in the proof of Theorem 4 below.

Proposition 8. *Consider a query language \mathcal{Q} for preference family \mathcal{P} on set of alternatives \mathcal{A} . Let C_1, \dots, C_K be all the simple necessary equivalence classes for \mathcal{P} . Let $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$ be any questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . Then $\Gamma \cap C_k \neq \emptyset$ for each $k = 1, \dots, K$, and therefore $|\Gamma| \geq K$, and so $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq K$.*

Suppose that $\Gamma \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$ is a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} that contains only simple necessary queries, and let Γ' be any equivalence-reduced version of Γ . Then $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) = |\Gamma'| = K$.

Proof: Consider any questionnaire Γ for \mathcal{P} , and let $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, and consider any $Q \in C_k$. Then Q is a simple necessary query for \mathcal{P} . Proposition 6 implies that Γ contains a query equivalent with Q and thus in C_k , and so $\Gamma \cap C_k \neq \emptyset$. Since the sets C_k are disjoint from each other, this implies that $|\Gamma| \geq K$, and, since Γ is an arbitrary questionnaire, we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \geq K$.

Lemma 6 implies that Γ' is a questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . The first part implies that $|\Gamma'| \geq K$. Also, $\Gamma' \subseteq \Gamma \subseteq C_1 \cup \dots \cup C_K$, and, for each k , $|\Gamma' \cap C_k| = 1$, since all elements of C_k are equivalent, and Γ' contains no different queries that are equivalent. Hence $|\Gamma'| \leq K$, so $|\Gamma'| = K$. This implies $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) \leq K$, so we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q}) = |\Gamma'| = K$. \square

For the language CompEx_A we need a variation of this result. For different $\alpha, \beta \in A$ we say that the query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta > \alpha\}$ is the twin of the query $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ (and vice versa). We say that $Q \in \text{CompEx}_A$ is for \mathcal{P} a *CompEx_A-simple necessary query* if there exists $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that (I) $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$, and (II) $Q \in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2}$, and any other query Q' in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} is equivalent to either Q or its twin.

Lemma 7. *Consider any CompEx_A -questionnaire Γ , and any CompEx_A -simple necessary query Q . Then Γ contains some query equivalent to either Q or its twin.*

Proof: Consider any CompEx_A -questionnaire Γ , and any CompEx_A -simple necessary query Q with associated elements w_1 and w_2 in W , so (I) $O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A) = \emptyset$, and (II) $Q \in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2}$, and any other query Q' in \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} is equivalent to either Q or its twin. In order to prove a contradiction, let us suppose that Γ doesn't contain any query equivalent to either Q or its twin. By (II), this implies that $\Gamma \cap \mathcal{Q}^{w_1, w_2} = \emptyset$, and so no query in Γ divides w_1 and w_2 .

Because the two parts of a CompEx_A -query are mutually exclusive, there exist unique configurations S_1 and S_2 of Γ such that $w_1 \in [S_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_2 \in [S_2]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Consider any query $Q' \in \Gamma$, and let ψ_1 and ψ_2 be the answers to that query in S_1 and S_2 , respectively, so that w_1 satisfies ψ_1 and w_2 satisfies ψ_2 . But, as argued above, Q' does not divide w_1 and w_2 , and thus, $\psi_1 = \psi_2$. Since Q' was an arbitrary query in Γ , this implies that configurations S_1 and S_2 are equal, so $w_1, w_2 \in [S_1]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

By definition of a $CompEx_A$ -questionnaire, there exists some $\beta \in A$ such that $[S_1]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$, which implies that $w_1, w_2 \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ and so $\beta \in O_{w_1}(A) \cap O_{w_2}(A)$, which contradicts (I) above. \square

5.3 Summary of results

All the lower bounds and upper bounds in the table are achievable. For example, the figure $\kappa - 1$ in the $CompEx_A$ row means that (a) for all A -preference families \mathcal{P} , $Depth(\mathcal{P}; CompEx_A) \leq \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$, and (b) for each $n \geq 1$ there exists a set of alternatives A and an A -preference family \mathcal{P} such that $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) = n$ and $Depth(\mathcal{P}; CompEx_A) = \kappa(\mathcal{P}) - 1$.

In Table 5.2 we sum up our results regarding the smallest and largest possible values of $Depth(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ and $MQS(\mathcal{P}; \mathcal{Q})$ (all expressible as a function of $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$) for the five types of query language \mathcal{Q} that we have considered in this paper.

	<i>Depth</i>	<i>MQS</i>
	lower bound, upper bound	lower bound, upper bound
$\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$	$\kappa - 1, \kappa - 1$	$\kappa - 1, \kappa - 1$
$\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt})$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \kappa - 1$
$\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt}')$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil$
$CompEx_A$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \kappa - 1$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\kappa - 1)$
$CompSym_A$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \kappa - 1$	$\lceil \log_2 \kappa \rceil, \frac{1}{2}\kappa(\kappa - 1)$

Table 1. Summary of general bounds on *Depth* and *MQS*, abbreviating $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ to κ . All bounds are achievable.

The results from the $\mathcal{Q}_A(\text{Opt})$ row come from Theorem 1. The results in the $\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt}')$ row are shown by Lemma 3 in Section 3.3. Regarding the $\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt})$ row:

- The equal lower and upper bound of the *Depth* value is shown by Theorem 2.
- The *MQS* upper bound: Theorem 1 shows the soundness of the upper bound, and the end of Section 3.2 shows that the upper bound can be achieved.
- Proposition 2 shows the soundness of the lower bound; it is achieved by any \mathcal{P} containing only total orders, since then $\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt})$ and $\mathcal{Q}_A^V(\text{Opt}')$ are equivalent.

Regarding the $CompEx_A$ and $CompSym_A$ rows:

- The soundness of the four lower bounds comes from Proposition 2. They are achieved by the lexicographic families in Section 4.3.
- The soundness of the two upper bounds on *Depth* comes from Proposition 4; they are achieved using approval families: see Theorem 3.
- The soundness and achievement of the two upper bounds on *MQS* is shown by Proposition 7.

6 Linear preference families

In this section we assume what we call a linear preference family \mathcal{P} , which is defined to be of the following form, for some $p \geq 1$. Each element of A is associated with a vector in \mathbb{R}^p , and to simplify notation we just assume $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$. We also assume that W is a closed convex polytope in \mathbb{R}^p , i.e., the intersection of a finite number of closed half-spaces. Component $\alpha(i)$ of an alternative α

will often represent the evaluation of α on the i^{th} objective, and $w(i)$ is the user's weight of that objective, so that the utility of α is $w \cdot \alpha = \sum_{i=1}^p w(i)\alpha(i)$. For $w \in W$ the relation \succ_w is thus defined by $\alpha \succ_w \beta \iff w \cdot \alpha \geq w \cdot \beta$, i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^p w(i)(\alpha(i) - \beta(i)) \geq 0$.

In the literature, W is often assumed to contain only vectors with non-negative components, and to be normalised in the sense that $\sum_{i=1}^p w(i) = 1$, or to have each $w(i)$ in $[0, 1]$.

The section uses a notion of adjacency of two alternatives: see Definition 1 below. Non-equivalent alternatives α and β are adjacent when the part of W where both are optimal is of maximum dimension, i.e., $\dim(W) - 1$. E.g., if $\dim(W) = 3$ then the sets $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ and $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ overlap in an area and not just a point or a line. The results of this section show that every minimum cardinality questionnaire consists just of a query equivalent to a comparison between α and β for each adjacent pair α and β .

For preference family \mathcal{P} we define the equivalence relation $\equiv_{\mathcal{P}}$ on A by $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \beta$ if and only if for all $w \in W$ we have $\alpha \equiv_w \beta$. Hence, in that case, no user model w in W distinguishes α and β . We say that A is (\mathcal{P} -)equivalence-free if the relation $\equiv_{\mathcal{P}}$ is just the equality relation, i.e., $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \beta$ (if and) only if $\alpha = \beta$. We can reduce any A to an equivalence-free subset, and this does not change any of the measures we are considering in this paper.

Eliminating equivalent alternatives doesn't change the values of *Depth* or *MQS*. We can thus assume, for notational convenience, that A is \mathcal{P} -equivalence-free.

The set $\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ of possibly strictly optimal alternatives is defined to be all $\alpha \in A$ such that there exists $w \in W$ with (i) $O_w(A) \ni \alpha$ and (ii) for all $\beta \in O_w(A)$ we have $\beta \equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \alpha$ (and thus, $O_w(A) = \{\alpha\}$ if A is \mathcal{P} -equivalence-free). Corollary 2 of [33] implies that $\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a \mathcal{P} -optimality cover for linear \mathcal{P} . Since A is \mathcal{P} -equivalence free, for any \mathcal{P} -optimality cover B we have $\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq B$ (since if $O_w(A) = \{\alpha\}$ then α must be in every optimality cover). $\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ is thus the unique setwise-minimal \mathcal{P} -optimality cover and $\kappa(\mathcal{P}) = |\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}|$.

Adjacency, as defined below, turns out to be a key concept. (The dimension $\dim(U)$ of a convex set U is the dimension of a largest dimension ball contained in U .)

Definition 1. Given linear \mathcal{P} on A and alternatives $\alpha, \beta \in A$ we say that α and β are (\mathcal{P} -)adjacent if they are both in $\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, and they are non- \mathcal{P} -equivalent, and $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ is of one less dimension than $W_{\mathcal{P}}$. For $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, define $\text{Adj}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ (abbreviated to $\text{Adj}(\alpha)$) to be the set of alternatives that are adjacent to α , i.e., the set of β such that β and α are adjacent.

Let U be the affine closure of W and so it has the same dimension as W , i.e., $\dim(U) = \dim(W)$. Thus, U is defined to be the (unique) smallest affine set containing W , which is the union of all (infinite) lines in \mathbb{R}^p whose intersection with W is a (non-trivial) line segment. $\dim(W)$ is therefore the dimension of the largest dimensional ball contained in W .

For $\gamma, \delta \in A$ we define $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ to be all $w \in W$ such that $\gamma \equiv_w \delta$, i.e., $w \cdot (\gamma - \delta) = 0$, so that $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma \geq \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} \cap [\delta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Let \mathcal{H} be the set of non-empty subsets of W of the form $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ over all non-equivalent $\gamma, \delta \in A$. \mathcal{H} is finite because A is finite. If a set $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ has dimension $\dim(W)$ then $w \cdot (\gamma - \delta) = 0$ for a set of dimension $\dim(W)$ which implies that $w \cdot (\gamma - \delta) = 0$ for all $w \in W$, contradicting the assumption that γ and δ are not equivalent. Thus the dimension of $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is at most $\dim(W) - 1$.

If α and β are adjacent we have $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \subseteq [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and so the dimension of $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is $\dim(W) - 1$.

We use a pair of lemmas for proving Proposition 9 below.

Lemma 8. *Assume that α and β are \mathcal{P} -adjacent. There exists some $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ such that the only element of \mathcal{H} containing v is $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$.*

Proof: Note first that for any $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ we have $v \in [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, i.e., $v \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$, because $v \cdot \alpha = v \cdot \beta$ since both α and β are optimal with respect to v .

In order to prove a contradiction, we suppose that for every $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ there exists another element of \mathcal{H} containing v (as well as $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$), and let \mathcal{H}' be $\mathcal{H} \setminus \{[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}\}$; then every element v of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ would be contained in some set in \mathcal{H}' , i.e., $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \subseteq \bigcup \mathcal{H}'$, and thus,

$$\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \subseteq \bigcup_{S \in \mathcal{H}'} S \cap [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}, \quad (2)$$

since $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \subseteq [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$. However, each set S' of the form $S \cap [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is the intersection with W of two different hyperplanes in U each of dimension at most $\dim(W) - 1$, and so $\dim(S') \leq \dim(W) - 2$. But then the right-hand-side of Equation 2 is a finite union of sets of dimension at most $\dim(W) - 2$, whereas the dimension of the left-hand-side of Equation 2 is $\dim(W) - 1$, (by definition of \mathcal{P} -adjacent), which is a contradiction. \square

We next give a very basic lemma regarding topological and convexity properties, which will be used multiple times in later proofs.

Lemma 9. *For any $\alpha, \beta \in A$, $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a convex and open subset of W , and $[\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a convex closed subset.*

Proof: We have $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is equal to all $w \in W$ such that $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) > 0$, so is an inverse image with respect to the continuous function $w \mapsto w \cdot (\alpha - \beta)$ of the open interval $(0, \infty)$, and thus, $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is an open subset of W . Similarly, $[\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is closed, since it is an inverse image of the closed subset $[0, \infty)$. Both sets are convex since they are intersections of half-spaces with the convex set W . \square

The technical lemma below shows the equivalences of queries of particular forms.

Lemma 10. *Consider linear \mathcal{P} , and alternatives $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in A$, with $\alpha \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \beta$ and $\gamma \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \delta$, and suppose that $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Then there exist γ', δ' with $\{\gamma', \delta'\} = \{\gamma, \delta\}$ such that $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma' > \delta']_{\mathcal{P}}$, $[\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma' \geq \delta']_{\mathcal{P}}$, and $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\delta' > \gamma']_{\mathcal{P}}$, and $[\beta \geq \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\delta' \geq \gamma']_{\mathcal{P}}$. The queries $\alpha \geq \beta$ and $\gamma \geq \delta$ in CompSym_A are \mathcal{P} -equivalent, as are the queries $\alpha > \beta$ and $\gamma' > \delta'$ in CompEx_A , and the queries $\beta > \alpha$ and $\delta' > \gamma'$.*

Proof: W is the disjoint union of convex sets $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and, similarly, the disjoint union of convex sets $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, $[\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

We will first show that $[\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ does not intersect with both $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Otherwise, if $u \in [\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $v \in [\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $u, v \in [\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, there exists a point w on the line segment between u and v with $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$, so $w \in [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$. But the convexity of $[\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ (see Lemma 9) implies $w \in [\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, which contradicts $w \in [\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Similarly, $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ does not intersect with both $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Hence, we have either $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ or $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Without loss of generality, assume the former.

Then we have $[\delta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} \cup [\delta \equiv \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} \cup [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Since $[\gamma \geq \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} = W \setminus [\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ this also implies $[\beta \geq \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma \geq \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and $[\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

This immediately implies that the queries $\alpha \geq \beta$ and $\gamma \geq \delta$ in CompSym_A are \mathcal{P} -equivalent, as are the queries $\alpha > \beta$ and $\delta > \gamma$ in CompEx_A , and the queries $\beta > \alpha$ and $\gamma > \delta$. \square

Proposition 9 below establishes that queries between adjacent alternatives are simple necessary queries (as defined in Section 5.2). The idea here is that one can pick w_1 and w_2 such that $O_{w_1}(A) = \{\alpha\}$ and $O_{w_2}(A) = \{\beta\}$, and that are sufficiently close to each other so that the only queries that divide them are the α - β queries.

Proposition 9. *Suppose that α and β are adjacent w.r.t. linear \mathcal{P} . Then there exist $w_1, w_2 \in W$ such that (a) $O_{w_1}(A) = \{\alpha\}$ and $O_{w_2}(A) = \{\beta\}$; and*

- (b) *the only queries that divide w_1 and w_2 in CompSym_A are $\alpha \geq \beta$ and equivalent queries, so $\alpha \geq \beta$ is a simple necessary query for CompSym_A ; and*
- (c) *the only queries that divide w_1 and w_2 in CompEx_A are $\alpha > \beta$ and $\beta > \alpha$, and equivalent queries.*

Proof: By Lemma 8 there exists $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ such that the only element of \mathcal{H} containing v is $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

For $\delta, \gamma \in A$, the set $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is an open and convex subset of W , by Lemma 9. Consider the intersection T of $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ over all $\gamma, \delta \in A$ such that $v \cdot (\delta - \gamma) > 0$ (i.e., such that $[\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} \ni v$). Then T is an open convex subset of W containing v , as the finite intersection of some open and convex sets containing v . We will show:

(*) the only set in \mathcal{H} that intersects with T is $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Firstly, both T and $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ contain v , so $[\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ intersects with T . For any other set $[\delta \equiv \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ in \mathcal{H} , this set does not contain v , and so either $v \cdot (\delta - \gamma) > 0$ or $v \cdot (\gamma - \delta) > 0$; without loss of generality, assume $v \cdot (\delta - \gamma) > 0$; then $T \subseteq [\delta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and so $u \cdot (\delta - \gamma) \neq 0$ for all $u \in T$, and so $[\delta \equiv \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ does not intersect with T , proving (*).

Since $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ there exists w_α that makes α strictly optimal, i.e., such that $w_\alpha \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) > 0$ for all $\gamma \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \alpha$, and so for all $\gamma \neq \alpha$, since A is equivalence-free. Because $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, for all $\gamma \in A$, $v \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) \geq 0$. Then for any u on the open line segment between w_α and v we have $u \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) > 0$. Because T is an open set containing v , it intersects with this open line segment, so there exists $w_1 \in T$ that makes α strictly optimal. Hence $O_{w_1}(A) = \{\alpha\}$. We can argue similarly for β to show that there exists $w_2 \in T$ such that $O_{w_2}(A) = \{\beta\}$, showing (a).

We have $\alpha \succ_{w_1} \beta$ and $\beta \succ_{w_2} \alpha$, so $w_1 \in [\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq [\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and $w_2 \in [\beta > \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq [\beta \geq \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}}$. This implies that query $\alpha \geq \beta$ in CompSym_A divides w_1 and w_2 , and that queries $\alpha > \beta$ and $\beta > \alpha$ in CompEx_A both divide w_1 and w_2 .

Consider any query $\gamma > \delta$ in CompEx_A that divides w_1 and w_2 . Then $w_i \in [\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $w_j \in [\delta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ where either $[i = 1 \text{ and } j = 2]$ or $[i = 2 \text{ and } j = 1]$. Since $w_i \cdot (\gamma - \delta) > 0$ and $w_j \cdot (\gamma - \delta) \leq 0$ there exists some point u on the closed line segment between w_1 and w_2 such that $u \cdot (\gamma - \delta) = 0$, and so $u \in [\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} \in \mathcal{H}$. The convexity of T implies that $u \in T$, because $w_1, w_2 \in T$. Thus, $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, since the latter is the only set in \mathcal{H} that intersects with T , by (*). Lemma 10 implies that the query $\gamma > \delta$ is equivalent to either query $\alpha > \beta$ or query $\beta > \alpha$. Hence, the only queries that divide w_1 and w_2 in CompEx_A are $\alpha > \beta$ and $\beta > \alpha$, and equivalent queries, showing part (c).

Similarly, if $\gamma \geq \delta$ is any query in CompSym_A that divides w_1 and w_2 , then the same argument shows that $[\gamma \equiv \delta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\alpha \equiv \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Lemma 10 implies that the query $\gamma \geq \delta$ in CompSym_A is equivalent to query $\alpha \geq \beta$. Therefore, the only queries that divide w_1 and w_2 in CompSym_A are $\alpha \geq \beta$ and equivalent queries.

Hence $\alpha \geq \beta$ is a simple necessary query for CompSym_A , and also $\alpha > \beta$ and $\beta > \alpha$ are CompEx_A -simple necessary queries, completing the proof of part (b). \square

We next give some technical lemmas, used in the proof of Proposition 10, starting with some basic topological and convexity properties.

For alternative $\gamma \in A$ we define $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ to be the subset of W for which γ is strictly optimal, which, since A is \mathcal{P} -equivalence-free is the set of $w \in W$ such that $O_w(A) = \{\gamma\}$. Thus, $\gamma \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ if and only if $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is non-empty.

Lemma 11. *Let $\alpha, \beta \in A$.*

- (i) *Each set $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is a convex and closed subset of W .*
- (ii) *$\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is a convex and open subset of W . If $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is non-empty then $\dim(\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)) = \dim(W)$.*
- (iii) *If $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is non-empty then the topological closure of it is $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$.*

Proof:

- (i) $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is the intersection over $\beta \in A$ of convex and closed subsets $[\gamma \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ of W (see Lemma 9) and so is a convex and closed subset of W .
- (ii) $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is the (finite) intersection over β not equivalent to γ of convex and open subsets $[\gamma > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ of W (see Lemma 9) and so is an open subset. Thus, if $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is non-empty then $\dim(\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)) = \dim(W)$, since it contains an open ball of W .

(iii) Suppose that $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is non-empty and let U be its topological closure (within W). Consider $w \in W \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, so that there exists $\beta \in A$ such that $w \cdot (\gamma - \beta) < 0$, i.e., $w \in [\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. The set $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is an open set disjoint from $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, so $U \not\ni w$. This proves that $U \cap (W \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)) = \emptyset$, i.e., $U \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$.

Now consider any $u \in \text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ and $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, and any $\beta \in A$ not equivalent to γ . Then, $u \cdot (\gamma - \beta) > 0$ and $v \cdot (\gamma - \beta) \geq 0$ and for any w_r on the open line segment between u and v where $w_r = ru + (1-r)v$ for some $r \in (0, 1)$, we have $w_r \cdot (\gamma - \beta) > 0$; this proves that $w_r \in \text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$. v is the limit of w_r as r tends to zero, and thus, v is in the topological closure of $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$. We have shown $U \supseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$, and hence, $U = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$.

Lemma 12. (i) *For any non-equivalent $\alpha, \beta \in A$, the dimension of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ is at most $\dim(W) - 1$.*

(ii) *$\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ has dimension $\dim(W)$ if and only if $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$.*

Proof: (i): To prove a contradiction, assume that $V = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ has dimension greater than or equal to $\dim(W)$. Since $V \subseteq W$ we have $\dim(V) \leq \dim(W)$ and so $\dim(V) = \dim(W)$. Then the affine closure V' of V contains W . For all $v \in V$ we have $v \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ (since both α and β are optimal with respect to v), and so this holds for all $v \in V'$, and in particular for all $v \in W$. This implies $\alpha \equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \beta$, contradicting our assumption of non-equivalence.

(ii): First assume that $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$. Then, by Lemma 11(ii), $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is an open subset of W . It is equal to the intersection of W with the half-spaces $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ for all β not equivalent with α . Since $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, we have that $\text{SO}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is non-empty, and, since it is open, it contains an open ball; any open ball has the same dimension as W , so $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ and thus, $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, has dimension $\dim(W)$.

To prove the converse, assume that $\alpha \notin \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$; we will show that $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ has dimension less than $\dim(W)$. Since $\alpha \notin \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, we have that $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is a subset of $\bigcup_{\beta \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \alpha} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$, and so $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) = \bigcup_{\beta \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \alpha} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$. Part (i) implies that each set $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ has dimension less than $\dim(W)$ and so, since A is finite, the union of these sets $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, has dimension less than $\dim(W)$. \square

Lemma 13. *Let $\gamma \in A$. If u is an interior point of W that is on the boundary of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ then there exists some $\beta \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \gamma$ with $\beta \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \ni u$.*

Proof: Let V be the union of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ over all $\beta \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \gamma$ such that $\beta \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$. We need to show that $V \ni u$. To prove a contradiction, assume that $V \not\ni u$. Since, by Lemma 11(i), V is a finite union of closed sets, it is closed, and so $W \setminus V$ is open. Thus, it contains an open ball T , and so, $T \cap V = \emptyset$.

Then $T' = T \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\gamma)$ is an open subset of W which does not intersect with any set $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ such that $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$. But the sets $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ over $\beta \in A$ cover W and, in particular, cover T' , and so $T' \subseteq \bigcup_{\beta \notin \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$. But by Lemma 12(ii), the right-hand-side is a finite union of convex sets of dimension less than that of W , and so has dimension at most $\dim(W) - 1$, whereas T' is an open set, which thus has dimension $\dim(W)$, giving the contradiction required. \square

In addition, we have the following sufficiency property. Although the proof of Proposition 10, is quite long, the idea is fairly simple: the hyperplanes $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ for $\beta \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$ form the highest dimensional parts of the boundary of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, and thus contain the whole boundary. This means that constraints $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) \geq 0$ for $\beta \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$ imply that $w \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, and so $\text{Adj}(\alpha)$ is an α -sufficient set.

Proposition 10. *For each $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, $\text{Adj}(\alpha)$ is an α -sufficient set.*

Proof: Consider any point $w \in W \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$. It is sufficient to show that there exists some $\beta \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$ such that $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) < 0$; because then, for $w' \in W$, if $w' \cdot (\alpha - \beta') \geq 0$ for all $\beta' \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$ we have $w' \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ showing that $\text{Adj}(\alpha)$ is an α -sufficient set.

The proof of this involves several stages, which we briefly summarise here.

- (i) We choose a point u in $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ that is not on the boundary of W .
- (ii) We let v be the point on the part of the line segment between w and u within $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ that is closest to W . Then v is on the boundary of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, and is not on the boundary $\partial(W)$ of W .
- (iii) There exists some facet F of the convex polytope $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ containing v . This is a convex polytope of dimension $\dim(\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)) - 1 = \dim(W) - 1$.
- (iv) We let E be the subset of F that is not on the boundary $\partial(W)$ of W , i.e., $E = F \setminus \partial(W)$. Then, $\dim(E) = \dim(F) = \dim(W) - 1$. We have $v \in E \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$.
- (v) Using Lemma 13, E is contained in $\bigcup_{\beta \neq \alpha} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ and so E is equal to $\bigcup_{\beta \neq \alpha} E_{\beta}$, where $E_{\beta} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap E \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$. Hence, there exists some $\beta \in A$ such that $\dim(E_{\beta}) = \dim(E)$, which implies that $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ has dimension at least $\dim(W) - 1$, which implies $\beta \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$.
- (vi) Since $E_{\beta} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ we have $x \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ for all $x \in E_{\beta}$, and thus, $x \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ for all x in the affine closure of E_{β} , and thus in particular for $x = v$.

- (vii) $u \cdot (\alpha - \beta) > 0$ and $v \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ then implies $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) < 0$, as required.

We now prove these points (i)–(vii) in detail.

Regarding (i), because $\alpha \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is non-empty, it has dimension $\dim(W)$, by Lemma 11(ii). This implies that $\text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is not a subset of $\partial(W)$, the boundary of W , since the latter is of smaller dimension. Choose any $u \in \text{SOpt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \setminus \partial(W)$, i.e., u that is not on the boundary of W and makes α strictly optimal. Thus, $u \cdot \alpha > u \cdot \delta$ for all $\delta \in A$ not equivalent with α , (i.e., for all $\delta \neq \alpha$, since A is assumed to be equivalence-free).

Since $w \in W \setminus \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ there exists some $\gamma \in A$ such that $w \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) < 0$. We have $u \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) > 0$ and $u \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, and $w \cdot (\alpha - \gamma) < 0$ and $w \notin \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ so, because $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is a closed set (by Lemma 11(i)), there exists some v which is an internal point on the line segment between u and w , that is the furthest point on the line segment from u such that $v \in \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, and thus, v is on the boundary of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$. Since u is an internal point of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, it is not on the boundary $\partial(W)$ of W , and so v is not either; (a boundary hyperplane of W is of the form $x \cdot \theta = t$; we have $u \cdot \theta > t$ and $w \cdot \theta \geq t$ and so $v \cdot \theta > t$). We have shown (ii).

Regarding (iii): because $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ is a convex polytope of dimension $\dim(W)$, every element on the boundary is on some facet F of the polytope, i.e., a polytope which is of dimension $\dim(W) - 1$ that is a subset of the boundary of $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ (see e.g., [17]); thus, we have $F \ni v$.

Let E be the set of points of the facet F that are not in the boundary $\partial(W)$ of W . Since the facet F is not a subset of $\partial(W)$, the intersection of the facet and the boundary of W is of lower dimension, so the dimension of E is the same as that of F , i.e., $\dim(W) - 1$. We have $v \in E \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \setminus \partial(W)$, showing (iv).

Since E is disjoint from the boundary of W , for each element x of E , using Lemma 13, there exists $\beta \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$ with $\beta \neq \alpha$ such that $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \ni x$, and thus, $x \in E_{\beta}$ where $E_{\beta} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap E$. Thus, E is equal to $\bigcup_{\beta \neq \alpha} \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap E$. Since A is finite, there exists some such $\beta \in A$ such that $E_{\beta} = \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta) \cap E$ also has dimension $\dim(W) - 1$. Because $E \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$, we have that $E_{\beta} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$. Then, $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ has dimension at least $\dim(W) - 1$, and so has dimension $\dim(W) - 1$, using Lemma 12(i) because $\alpha \not\equiv_{\mathcal{P}} \beta$ (using the fact that A is \mathcal{P} -equivalence-free). Hence, we have $\beta \in \text{Adj}(\alpha)$, showing (v).

Since $E_{\beta} \subseteq \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha) \cap \text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\beta)$ we have $x \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ for all $x \in E_{\beta}$, and thus, $x \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$ for all x in the affine closure of E_{β} . Since $\dim(E_{\beta}) = \dim(W) - 1 = \dim(F)$ we have that F is contained in the affine closure of E_{β} which implies, in particular, that $v \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = 0$, showing (vi).

We also have $u \cdot (\alpha - \beta) > 0$ (because α is strictly optimal with respect to u) and v is on the interior of the line segment between u and w , so we can write $v = ru + (1 - r)w$ for some $r \in (0, 1)$, and thus, $v \cdot (\alpha - \beta) = ru \cdot (\alpha - \beta) + (1 - r)w \cdot (\alpha - \beta)$. This implies (vii) $w \cdot (\alpha - \beta) < 0$, as required. \square

This leads to the following theorem that determines the minimum CompSym_A -questionnaire size for linear \mathcal{P} (and a corresponding questionnaire) and, in fact, this is the same size as the minimum for CompEx_A , as shown by Theorem 5 below.

Theorem 4. *For linear \mathcal{P} let $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$ be the set of queries $\{\beta \geq \gamma, \gamma \geq \beta\}$ over all adjacent $\beta, \gamma \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$. Then $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$ is a CompSym_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} containing only simple necessary queries, and $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) = |\Gamma'|$, where Γ' is any equivalence-reduced version of $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$.*

Proof: Let $B = \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$, and for all $\alpha \in B$ let $D_{\alpha} = \text{Adj}(\alpha) \subseteq \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}} = B$. Proposition 10 implies that, for each $\alpha \in B$, $\text{Adj}(\alpha)$ is an α -sufficient set, and Proposition 5 then implies that $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$ is a CompSym_A -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} . Proposition 9 implies that each query in $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$ is a simple necessary query. Let Γ' be any equivalence-reduced version of $\Gamma(\text{Adj})$. Proposition 8 implies that $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) = |\Gamma'|$. \square

We give some lemmas that will be used to prove Theorem 5 below.

Lemma 14. *Let $\beta, \gamma \in A$, and suppose that $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is non-empty. Then (i) $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ both have dimension $\dim(W)$, and (ii) $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is the topological closure of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ within W .*

Proof: (i) By Lemma 9, $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is an open set in W , and, since it is non-empty, there exists an open ball within it, which has dimension $\dim(W)$, so $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ has dimension $\dim(W)$. Since $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq [\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}} \subseteq W$, we have that $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ also has dimension $\dim(W)$.

(ii) This makes use of the convexity of W . Consider any $u \in [\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and any $v \in [\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. The open line segment L between u and v is a subset of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ because for any $w \in L$, $w \cdot (\beta - \gamma)$ is a weighted average of $u \cdot (\beta - \gamma) (> 0)$ and $v \cdot (\beta - \gamma) (\geq 0)$, and so $w \cdot (\beta - \gamma) > 0$, and $w \in [\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Thus, v is in the topological closure of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$; this shows that $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a subset of the topological closure of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Now consider any point w in W that is not in $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Then, because $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a closed set, by Lemma 9, $W \setminus [\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is an open set, so there exists an open ball around w which does not intersect with $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. This implies that w is not in the topological closure of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$; hence, $[\beta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is equal to the topological closure of $[\beta > \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. \square

Lemma 15. *Consider some linear preference family \mathcal{P} . Assume that $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ is a non-empty proper subset of W . Suppose that the CompEx_A query $\{\alpha > \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ is \mathcal{P} -equivalent to $\{\gamma > \delta, \delta \geq \gamma\}$. Then the CompSym_A query $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ is \mathcal{P} -equivalent to $\{\gamma \geq \delta, \delta \geq \gamma\}$.*

Proof: If $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\delta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$ then Lemma 9 implies that this non-empty set is both an open and closed proper subset of W , which contradicts the fact that a convex set is connected. Hence, we have that $[\alpha > \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma > \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $[\beta \geq \alpha]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\delta \geq \gamma]_{\mathcal{P}}$. Lemma 14(ii) implies that $[\alpha \geq \beta]_{\mathcal{P}} = [\gamma \geq \delta]_{\mathcal{P}}$, and hence, $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \beta \geq \alpha\}$ is \mathcal{P} -equivalent to $\{\gamma \geq \delta, \delta \geq \gamma\}$. \square

Theorem 5. *For linear \mathcal{P} we have $\text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompSym}_A) = \text{MQS}(\mathcal{P}; \text{CompEx}_A)$.*

Proof: Consider any CompEx_A -questionnaire Γ . For adjacent pair $\{\alpha, \beta\}$, by Proposition 9, $\alpha > \beta$ is a CompEx_A -simple necessary query, and so, by Lemma 7, Γ contains a query $Q_{\alpha, \beta}$ equivalent to either $\alpha > \beta$ or to $\beta > \alpha$. Let Γ_1 be the set of all $Q_{\alpha, \beta}$ over all adjacent pairs $\{\alpha, \beta\}$, so $\Gamma_1 \subseteq \Gamma$.

For $Q \in \Gamma_1$, let Q^{\geq} be the corresponding query in CompSym_A , and let Γ^{\geq} be the set of all queries Q^{\geq} such that $Q \in \Gamma_1$. We have $|\Gamma^{\geq}| \leq |\Gamma_1| \leq |\Gamma|$, so $|\Gamma^{\geq}| \leq |\Gamma|$.

Consider any adjacent pair $\{\gamma, \delta\}$. There exists some $Q = Q_{\gamma, \delta} \in \Gamma_1 \subseteq \Gamma$ that is equivalent to either $\gamma > \delta$ or $\delta > \gamma$. By Lemma 15, Q^{\geq} is equivalent to $\{\gamma \geq \delta, \delta \geq \gamma\}$. So, Γ^{\geq} contains a query equivalent to each query in Δ , where Δ is the set of adjacent pair queries $\{\beta \geq \gamma, \gamma \geq \beta\}$ over all adjacent $\beta, \gamma \in \text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}$.

Theorem 4 implies that Δ is a $CompSym_A$ -questionnaire for \mathcal{P} , and so Lemma 6 implies that Γ^\geq is a $CompSym_A$ -questionnaire, and thus, $MQS(\mathcal{P}; CompSym_A) \leq |\Gamma^\geq| \leq |\Gamma|$. Since Γ is an arbitrary $CompEx_A$ -questionnaire, we have $MQS(\mathcal{P}; CompSym_A) \leq MQS(\mathcal{P}; CompEx_A)$, and hence they are equal, by Proposition 3. \square

7 Discussion

We have developed a formal framework for the analysis of the number N of binary queries required to return an optimal alternative, given a family \mathcal{P} of preference orders, considering a dynamic (i.e., interactive) version of the problem, using query trees, which enable the choice of query to depend on the answers to previous queries; and a static (batch) version of the problem, using a set of queries that we call a questionnaire. We have shown that a (somewhat complex) query language can achieve the logarithmic lower bound on the number of queries. For the more natural comparison query languages, we prove upper and lower bounds on N of a very simple form and give preference families that achieve those bounds. For the important linear case we show that N can be characterised simply for the static problem, i.e., for the minimum questionnaire size.

The focus of this paper was not at all on complexity or computational issues, but our results certainly do have relevance in that direction. For instance, it would appear to follow from Theorem 4 and associated results that a minimum cardinality questionnaire can be computed in polynomial time in $|A|$ for the linear case.

The results are also suggestive for algorithmic methods for interactive optimisation. Many approaches in the literature use minimax regret as a measure of closeness to necessary optimality. Since $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ is involved in both upper and lower bounds of *Depth* and *MQS*, this suggests that $\kappa(\mathcal{P})$ (i.e., $|\text{PSO}_{\mathcal{P}}|$ for the linear case) seems then a very natural and potentially useful measure of closeness to necessary optimality, which can be used instead of max regret.

The current framework relates only to a single decision maker. It could also be very fruitful to develop an analogous framework for multi-agent preference elicitation, building on works such as [18] and [29].

Like other works in the literature on interactive optimisation, our framework assumes that the user preference models are total pre-orders (and, for instance, linear preferences, as considered in Section 6, are total pre-orders). However, the framework can be extended to the more general case where preference orders can be arbitrary pre-orders (reflexive and transitive relations, that may not be complete). The notation $O_w(A)$ is then re-interpreted as the set of α that are undominated in A with respect to \succsim_w (i.e., such that if $\beta \in A$ and $\beta \succsim_w \alpha$ then $\alpha \succsim_w \beta$); and so $\text{Opt}_{\mathcal{P}}(\alpha)$ becomes the set of $w \in W_{\mathcal{P}}$ such that α is undominated with respect to \succsim_w . The definitions and results in Sections 2 and 3 generalise easily, and also some of the results in Sections 4 and 5 when one redefines the language $CompEx_A$ to contain queries of the form $\{\alpha \geq \beta, \neg(\alpha \geq \beta)\}$.

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